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QUANTIFICATION OF LMT SCALING SCENARIOS

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Short Summary of results
<p>This report summarizes the methodologies, assumptions, and results of quantifying of input data for simulation experiments with a global coupled model system representing two scenarios scaling-up land-use based mitigation technologies to the regional to global level. Four complete dataset have been prepared, including a “Reference” scenario, a “Corrected Reference” scenario and two LMT scaling scenarios called “High CDR Ambition” and “Moderate CDR Ambition” (CDR=carbon dioxide removal). In “High CDR Ambition”, there is strong focus on maximizing CDR with cost-intensive high-tech LMTs such as bioenergy with carbon capture and storage (BECCS) requiring large-scale implementation. Other LMTs with lower CDR potential are deployed on a rather low level despite their co-benefits for other goals of sustainable development. In contrast, the LMT portfolio in “Moderate CDR Ambition” draws more on nature-based solutions with co-benefits addressing other environmental problems (i.e. agroforestry) and technologies that can be implement on relatively small scales with lower financial resources. For all scenario, a dataset comprising a consistent set of time series in 5-yr time steps until 2010 on country level, informing the deployment of the Afforestation/Reforestation LMT, the no/reduced tillage LMT, the Agroforestry LMT, the BECCS LMT and the PyCCS LMT (pyrolysis with carbon capture and storage in from of biochar). Contextual data determining the development of the agricultural sector, e.g. cropland area, was derived from model results of an Integrated Assessment Model.</p>
Evidence of accomplishment
This report

Preface

Negative emission solutions are expected to play a pivotal role in future climate actions and net zero emissions policy scenarios. To date most climate actions have focussed on phasing out fossil fuels and reducing greenhouse gas emissions in, for example, industry, electricity, and transport. While zero emission trajectories in these sectors will remain a priority for decades to come, it is expected that residual GHG emissions will remain. To be able to fulfil the Paris Agreement and meet the world's climate goals research, policy and markets are increasingly looking at negative emission solutions.

This is why the nineteen LANDMARC consortium partners work together in order to:

- Estimate the climate impact of land-based negative emission solutions, in agriculture, forestry, and other land-use sectors
- Assess the potential for regional and global upscaling of negative emission solutions
- Map their potential environmental, economic, and social co-benefits and trade-offs

LANDMARC is an interdisciplinary consortium with expertise from ecology, engineering, climate sciences, global carbon cycle, soil sciences, satellite earth observation sciences, agronomy, economics, social sciences, and business. There is a balanced representation of partners from academia, SMEs, and NGOs from the EU, Africa, Asia and the Americas, which ensures a wide coverage of LMTs operating in different contexts (e.g. climates, land-use practices, socio-economic etc.) and spatial scales.

The LANDMARC project consortium:

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Executive summary

In the LANDMARC project, a set of scenarios of possible future scaling of land-use based mitigation technologies (LMT) was developed on the regional to continental level. The scenarios include a qualitative and a quantitative part. The qualitative part are alternative narratives, or what we call storylines, describing the deployment of individual LMTs in a portfolio along with a characterization of factors promoting or impeding their implementation (i.e. constraints and enablers). These storylines were developed in a stakeholder engagement-process and focus on four larger world regions in South-East Asia, Europe, Latin America, and Africa. The quantitative part is a model-based analysis of climate mitigation effects of the LMT implementation outlined in the storylines. For this purpose, a coupled global simulation model that combines the climate model EC-Earth3-CC and the land-use change model LandSHIFT-G was developed in the course of the project. LandSHIFT-G simulates sequences of land-use by integrating assumptions on the future development of the agricultural sector (e.g. crop/livestock production) and assumptions on the deployment of selected LMTs. Based on these land-use/land-cover changes (LUCC), EC-Earth3-CC simulates potential effects on climate variables, vegetation (both natural and managed) and atmospheric CO₂ concentrations. Changing potential crop yields because of climate change as modelled by the dynamic vegetation model LPJ-GUESS, a component of EC-Earth3-CC, feed back to the land-use model, potentially affecting subsequent land-use patterns.

The purpose of Deliverable 6.3 is documenting the translation-process of selected elements of the scenario storylines into quantitative model inputs specifying the deployment of LMTs for alternative global LMT scaling scenarios, together with contextual information on the evolution of land-use related sectors. The scaling scenarios follow the logic that the two main uncertainties for future land-use based climate mitigation are the levels of “climate mitigation ambition” and “regional engagement”. We developed two alternative scenarios called “*High CDR Ambition*” and “*Moderate CDR Ambition*”. Here, the terms “high” and “moderate” mainly refer to the level of carbon dioxide removal (CDR) achieved with land-use based solutions. We assumed that high level of ambition coincides with a high level of regional engagement, as significant increases in CDR will require more investment in capital-intensive, high-tech LMTs on a large-scale with significant infrastructure requirements and biomass mobilization needs such as bioenergy with carbon capture and storage (BECCS). Although such LMTs have a relatively large potential of CDR, they are often not suitable to counteract other environmental problems, such as biodiversity loss and soil degradation. On the contrary, the extensive deployment of LMTs one-dimensionally focusing on CDR will potentially worsen environmental conditions, e.g., due to extensive monocultures of bioenergy feedstock. Accordingly, the “*High CDR Ambition*” scenario focuses on the large-scale implementation of cost-intensive LMTs (i.e. BECCS) trying to maximize the CDR potential, while the LMT portfolio in “*Moderate CDR Ambition*” draws more on nature-based solutions with co-benefits addressing other environmental problems (i.e. agroforestry).

The required model input includes time series of driving factors depicting the basic development of the simulated land-use system such as population, agricultural production and crop yield changes due to technological change as well as forcing data of the simulated climate system such as greenhouse gas emissions, solar radiation and concentration of greenhouse gases in the atmosphere. This

information comes from already published global scenarios combining Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSP) and Representative Concentration Pathways (RCPs). The “*Moderate CDR Ambition*” scenario is driven by results of SSP2-RCP2.6 (~2° warming) while the “*High CDR Ambition*”-scenario is driven by results of SSP2-RCP1.9 (~1.5° warming). In addition, we define a reference scenario without additional LMT implementation based on the SSP2-RCP4.5 (~2.7° warming). In addition to these basic drivers, we specify information on LMT implementation as defined in the scaling scenarios. Currently the model system can simulate the LMTs i) no-till agriculture, ii) agroforestry, iii) afforestation/reforestation as well as iv) bioenergy production in combination with carbon capture and storage.

This deliverable transparently documents the translation process from qualitative storylines derived from stakeholders into quantitative model input and provides a detailed description of the input data used in the simulation experiments with the global coupled model. Further, it discusses potential uncertainties and limitations of the translation process that need to be considered when interpreting the simulation results.

1 Introduction

A significant amount of carbon dioxide removal (CDR) will likely be required to reach the Paris Agreement goal of limiting the global average temperature increase to 1.5°C in this century, which will require net zero global emissions around 2050 (Lee et al., 2023). CDR may be realized by land-based mitigation technologies and practices (LMTs) along with other negative emission technologies in non-land sectors, such as Direct Air Carbon Capture and Storage (DACCS) or ocean-based sequestration methods. However, there are major uncertainties regarding their negative emissions potential and mechanisms of commercialization (Hickey et al., 2023; Terlouw et al., 2021). Whereas the LMTs considered in LANDMARC are, with the exception of bioenergy with carbon capture and storage (BECCS), already deployed and/or widely available, the non-land CDR options are not yet available, especially in lower and medium income regions. Non-land CDR option and BECCS are more capital-intensive and may challenge biodiversity and sustainable development goals. The implementation of stakeholder processes can help to better understand constraints and enablers as documented in LADMARC D6.2 (“Regional Engagement for Global impact”).

In WP 6 of LANDMARC (Task 6.3), a set of scenarios of possible future scaling up of land-use based mitigation technologies (LMT) was developed on the regional to continental scale (D6.2). The scenarios were developed over time as a set of alternative storylines qualitatively describing the deployment of individual LMTs in a portfolio along with a characterization of factors promoting or impeding their implementation (i.e. constraints and enablers). Such storylines were developed as part of stakeholder engagement processes focusing on four larger regions in South-East Asia (ASEAN countries), Europe (EU27), Latin America (The Amazon Cooperation Treaty Organisation), and Africa (East African Community) (see LANDMARC Deliverable D6.2 for details).

Another objective of LANDMARC was the quantitative analysis of climate mitigation effects of LMT scaling with a coupled global simulation model integrating a land-use model and a climate model (WP7). To support this, Task 6.4 of WP6 was designed to translate selected elements of the regional scenario narratives into quantitative model inputs specifying the deployment of LMTs for two alternative global scenarios, together with contextual information on the evolution of land-use related sectors. The quantitative scenarios covered five LMTs supported by the coupled model system including reduced/no-till agriculture, agroforestry, afforestation/reforestation, BECCS, and the production of biofuels from pyrolysis of biomass in combination with carbon capture in form of biochar (PyCCS).

The purpose of this Deliverable D6.3 is to document the methodology and assumptions used for the quantification of the global LMT scaling scenarios and to present the resulting model inputs to be used in the simulation experiments (Task 7.2). It is complementary to deliverable D6.2 summarizing the activities and results of the stakeholder engagement process (Task 6.3). The model results on climate mitigation effects of the LMT scaling scenarios will be documented in the deliverables D7.2 (“Climate projections and LMT effects on global carbon cycle”) and D.7.3 (“Decadal climate predictions and LMT effects on global carbon cycle”), while an economic and environmental

evaluation of the simulated land-use changes will be provided in D7.4 (“Economic and environmental effects of LMT implementation”).

This report first outlines the general logic of the LMT scaling scenarios along with the framework conditions of the scenario development and the role of stakeholders in scenario quantification (chapter 2). We then briefly summarize the main components of the coupled model system explaining the nature of the model input requirements (chapter 3). The methodology used to quantify the model inputs and the assumption made based on literature research, stakeholder feedback, or own considerations by researchers responsible for Task 6.4 is presented in chapter 4, while the resulting input datasets are summarized in chapter 5. Finally, the report is wrapped up with a reflection on the limitations of the methodology and resulting datasets (chapter 5) and conclusions (chapter 7).

2 Development of LMT scaling scenarios

The LMT scaling scenarios developed in LANDMARC on the regional to global scale generally follow the logic that the two main uncertainties for future land-use based climate mitigation are the levels of “climate mitigation ambition” and “regional engagement”.

We developed two alternative LMT scaling scenarios called “*High CDR Ambition*” and “*Moderate CDR Ambition*”. Here, the terms “high” and “moderate” mainly refer to the level of carbon dioxide removal (CDR) achieved with land-use based solutions.

We assume that high level of ambition must coincide with a high level of regional engagement due to the fact that significant increases in CDR will require more investment in capital-intensive, high-tech LMTs on a large-scale with significant infrastructure requirements and biomass mobilization needs such as BECCS (Smith et al., 2023). As these requirements likely exceed the capacities of most countries individually, close collaboration between countries in a region (so-called “regional engagement”) - based on contractual regulations of technical and financial details - is crucial for high CDR ambitions. Although such LMTs have a relatively large CDR potential, they are often not suitable to counteract other environmental problems, such as biodiversity loss and soil degradation. On the contrary, the extensive deployment of LMTs with one-dimensional focus on CDR will potentially worsen environmental conditions, e.g., due to extensive monoculture of bioenergy feedstock. Hence, a future development with moderate goals of CDR in the land-use sector but aiming at a more balanced performance to counteract multiple environmental issues likely focuses on other more nature-based LMTs. Also for the successful implementation of nature-based solutions, additional “regional engagement” is important because climate mitigation can only be successful if a substantial part of the countries worldwide is willing and able to make their fair contribution. The willingness to act strongly depends on the confidence that investment in LMTs will not impair a country’s economic competitiveness, while ability to act is promoted by international collaboration, e.g., through knowledge transfer and financial support. However, compared to the level of regional engagement needed to implement, e.g. cross-country BECCs facilities, the level of regional engagement required for nature-based LMTs can be considered moderate. These nature based solutions, including

agriculture and forestry LMTs, can be undertaken at various scales and by a wider range of actors. Most of these LMTs can be implemented with lower upfront capital costs and investment risks (see also D6.2) if the land use practice is already in place (agriculture land applying LMT practice) although there are exceptions of more costly LMTs such as peatland rewetting (which is not covered by our models).

Accordingly, the “High CDR Ambition” scenario focuses on the large-scale implementation of cost-intensive LMTs (i.e. BECCS) trying to maximize the CDR potential, while the LMT portfolio in the “Moderate CDR Ambition” scenario draws more on nature-based solutions with co-benefits addressing other environmental problems (i.e. agroforestry).

Overall, the work presented in this report follows the concept that the scenario logic indicates to which degree individual LMTs are deployable, including regional differences in volume and dynamics. The main characteristics (LMT portfolio) of an LMT scaling scenario result from the combination of the projections by LMT.

Table 1 Overview of the main characteristics of the LMT scaling scenarios "High CDR Ambition" and "Moderate CDR Ambition"

		Level of CDR Ambition	
		Moderate	High
Level of Regional Engagement	Moderate	<p><i>“Moderate CDR Ambition”</i></p> <p>High cost LMTs only in high income countries</p> <p>Large-scale technical solutions implemented only in large countries</p> <p>More nature-based solutions</p> <p>Co-benefits reducing biodiversity loss</p>	
	High		<p><i>“High CDR Ambition”</i></p> <p>High-cost and large-scale LMTs possible due to international collaboration</p> <p>Strong focus on CDR</p> <p>Co-benefits less important</p>

2.1 Framework conditions of the scenario quantification

The task of developing the global LMT scaling scenarios (Task 6.4) was carried out in close collaboration with the tasks of model development (Task 7.1) and simulation experiments with the global couple model (Task 7.2). Hence, personnel and technical resources allocated to these tasks in combination with limitations of the coupled model system and its input requirements result in number of constraints for the scenario development:

- In order to analyze the mitigation potential of LMT portfolios, simulation results of the LMT scaling scenarios must be compared to results of a reference scenario, which constitute the context of LMT implementation.
- The number of alternative scenarios including the reference scenario was limited to three.
- The resources of the project did not cover the preparation of a complete input dataset (context) for the coupled model system. However, the climate model had previously been applied for the widely used reference scenario in the climate modelling community representing a combination of SSP2 (share socio-economic pathway, O'Neill et al., 2017) and RCP4.5 (representative concentration pathway, van Vuuren et al., 2011). Hence, SSP2-RCP4.5 was set as the reference as the complete input dataset for the climate model was already available and ready for use and input data for LandSHIFT-G could also be derived easily from existing data. SSP2 is a “Middle-of-the-road” scenario with medium challenges to climate mitigation and adaptation (Hausfather, 2018).
- The capabilities of the coupled models did not support the sound representation of all LMTs considered relevant (e.g. the 13 LMTs identified in deliverable D6.1). In total, the coupled model system could be extended to cover five LMTs in a simplified manner (see 3.3), constraining the LMT portfolio that could be deployed in the scenarios. The final set of LMTs covered by the model constitutes a compromise between the confidence in the accuracy of the model representation and relevance of LMTs, e.g., stressed by case study leads. For instance, the agroforestry LMT, which was initially considered too complex, was added in a very simple way after discussions with LANDMARC case study leads and members of the scientific advisory board during the first in-person General Assembly meeting in April 2022. In contrast, the request of adding a peatland management LMT had to be refused by the modelling team.
- Although the global coupled model system works on individual countries internally, in order to create some consistency and allow more useful comparisons across countries and regions, only LMTs relevant on the global scale (i.e. in different world regions) were considered.
- With the given resources allocated in Task 6.4, it was only possible to prepare input data that could be derived from consistent datasets with global coverage in a semi-automated manner. The collection and integration of new data based on heterogeneous national information would have been too elaborate and time-consuming.
- The system boundary of the climate model comprises the whole planet. Hence, only scenarios with global coverage could be modelled. Although regional differences in the volume and dynamics of LMT deployment were to be considered, each scenario had to be a global combination of a single selected narrative per region.

2.2 The role of stakeholder engagement

The quantification of LMT scaling scenarios for global modelling was closely connected to the stakeholder engagement process organized by Task 6.3. In a first step, a preliminary quantification of two alternative scenario input datasets was carried out in Task 6.4. The input datasets fulfilled the requirements of the coupled model system and were consistent with the decision that the main

scenario uncertainties were the levels of climate mitigation ambition and regional engagement (see above). Subsequently, preliminary model simulations (using a simplified modeling system consisting of LANDSHIFT-G and LPJ-GUESS) were conducted based on these scenario inputs. At a series of regional stakeholder workshops, the preliminary scenarios assumptions and model results were presented to provide one of the evidence bases for initiating and framing a discussion about future LMT deployment. Feedback from stakeholders was expected to inform the revision of the input datasets leading to input data for the simulation of the final LMT scaling scenarios. Ideally, the revision should be based on a systematic sensitivity analysis of the modelled climate to different levels of LMT deployment. However, this was beyond the scope of LANDMARC because the necessary number of model runs would have exceeded the available resources. Moreover, it would have been difficult to convey the complex findings of such a sensitivity analysis to stakeholders given the limited amount of time available at the workshops. Thus, the presentation of assumptions and methods underlying the input data along with the preliminary model results at the workshops must be considered an example-based demonstration of the modelling exercise of WP7, which helped stakeholders to understand better the nature of the input data needed for the models and the expected model results. In this way, the modeling framework and the stakeholder storylines developed in each region serve to complement each other by providing a broad characterization of enhanced or upscaled climate ambition alongside the context of regional engagement and international cooperation (see also LANDMARC Deliverable D6.2). Consequently, the revision of the input assumptions was not informed by preliminary model results but by a rather general discussion about individual LMTs. Hence, this report describes the assumptions for the preliminary model runs and their revision but does not present preliminary results of the coupled model (refer to annex of LANDMARC Deliverable D6.2¹). The results of the final simulation runs will be described in the LANDMARC project Deliverables D7.2, D7.3, and D7.4.

The mismatch of LMTs considered important by stakeholders (e.g. BECCS based on forestry residues) and those covered by the coupled model system (e.g. BECCS based on purpose grown bioenergy crops), in combination with the high level of simplification needed for a global modelling approach, are responsible for limited stakeholder feedback on the inputs needed by the model. Thus, the information from stakeholders covered the information required by the model only partially and/or in broader terms. In turn, stakeholders were critical for a number of assumptions (e.g. very optimistic crop yield improvements), which could not be changed during the revision because the required model development was too elaborate or alternative datasets were not available (e.g. IAM results assuming less optimistic yield improvements). Hence, we did not try to achieve a 1:1 relationship between storylines and input of global scenario (see also LANDMARC Deliverable D6.2). Although the coupled model was limited in type and number of LMTs it could cover, it provided the rigor of a systematic and internally consistent analysis of their mitigation effect. In contrast, the qualitative storylines were highly flexible in expressing what stakeholders considered relevant (e.g.

¹ Annex D2: Modelling Assumptions and Results by region for Coupled Model (Landshift and LPJ-Guess)

choice of LMTs) but needed to be connected to—or anchored in—the quantitative physical land-climate models, in order to reconcile the qualitative descriptions with the actual mitigation effects and feasibility. As each element was incomplete by itself, the model-based analysis complemented the qualitative storylines and vice-versa.

3 Model input requirements of the coupled model system

The scenario input data summarized in this report is tailored to feed in a coupled modelling system consisting of EC-Earth3-CC (Döscher et al., 2021) and LandSHIFT-G (Schaldach et al., 2011; Schüngel et al., 2022), which is used to analyze the effects of the implementation of LMT portfolios on climate at the global scale. LandSHIFT-G models sequences of land-use by integrating assumptions on the future development of the agricultural sector (e.g. crop/livestock production) and assumptions on the deployment of selected LMTs. Based on these land-use/land-cover changes (LUCC), EC-Earth3-CC simulates potential effects on climate variables, vegetation (both natural and managed) and atmospheric CO₂ concentrations. Changing potential crop yields and growth of natural vegetation influenced by climate change as modelled by the dynamic vegetation model LPJ-GUESS (Lindeskog et al., 2013; Smith et al., 2014), a component of EC-Earth3-CC, are fed back to the land-use model, potentially affecting subsequent land-use patterns. The model system is described in more detail in Deliverable D7.1 of the LANDMARC project. This chapter gives an overview of the input time series needed for individual components of the models in order to carry out simulation runs of LMT scaling scenarios. The key aspects of the modelling approach and new features not yet covered by D7.1 are summarized briefly as far as it is necessary to explain the required model inputs.

3.1 Basic input requirements for LandSHIFT-G

The scenario model drivers for LandSHIFT-G comprise time series (in 5-year steps) by country including:

- Population;
- Demand for crop production under irrigated management (by crop type);
- Yield change due to technological improvements for irrigated crops (not including climate change effects);
- Demand for crop production under rain-fed management (by crop type);
- Yield change due to technological improvements for rain-fed crops (not including climate change effects); and
- Demand for feed and forage production.

Production and crop yield change must be specified for each desired crop-management combination. Typically, those inputs are aggregated to a reasonable number (~5-12) of crop types or classes of crop types in way that the observed amount of total cropland or crop production is sufficiently well represented by the data. The crop types specified for LANDMARC, which are harmonized between LandSHIFT-G and LPJ-GUESS using the crop types of the Land-Use Harmonization Dataset (LUH2;

Hurt et al., 2020) are listed in Table 2. Global coverage of relevant land-use change in the LANDMARC version of LandSHIFT-G is achieved by a setup for 166 countries. A small number of small countries, mainly islands (e.g. Malta), that are not represented by at least one grid cell of the climate model were omitted.

Table 2 Crop types considered by LPJ-GUESS and LandSHIFT-G

Crop name	Management	Abbreviation
Annual C3-plants	rain-fed	CC3ann
Perennial C3-plants	rain-fed	CC3per
N-fixing C3-plants	rain-fed	CC3nfx
Annual C4-plants	rain-fed	CC4ann
Perennial C4-plants	rain-fed	CC4per
Annual C3-plants	irrigated	CC3anni
Perennial C3-plants	irrigated	CC3peri
N-fixing C3-plants	irrigated	CC3nfxi
Annual C4-plants	irrigated	CC4anni
Perennial C4-plants	irrigated	CC4peri
2nd generation bioenergy crops	rain-fed	CCmis

3.2 EC-Earth-CC/LPJ-Guess

The input data for the atmospheric component (IFS) of the climate model EC-Earth-CC, also referred to as forcings, include:

- Global concentrations of GHG (CO₂, CH₄, N₂O) and other gases (e.g. O₃, cfc);
- CO₂ anthropogenic emissions;
- Aerosols, aerosol precursors and other reactive compounds (emissions or concentrations);
- Ozone and other well-mixed gases; and
- Solar forcings.

The forcings for the land/vegetation component (LPJ-GUESS) include:

- Global concentrations of CO₂;
- Nitrogen deposition, fertilizer input; and
- LUH2 land-use types and transitions and crop types.

Additional input requirements on land-use change, including the deployment of LMTs, are generated dynamically by LandSHIFT-G and passed to LPJ-GUESS during a simulation run.

3.3 Input data controlling LMT deployment

The input requirements of the coupled model systems to control the various LMTs are described in this section, along with a brief summary of the modelling approach to represent the LMT.

3.3.1 No/reduced tillage LMT

Agricultural management without tillage or with reduced tillage can lead to higher soil carbon contents than conventional management with tillage. This is because tillage enhances the aerobic decomposition of organic material in soils (e.g. humus). Hence, a transition from conventional to no/reduced tillage practices might mitigate climate change as it leads to a net flux of carbon from the atmosphere to soils.

No/reduced tillage is represented by the assumption that a share s_{nt} of the area allocated for each crop type by LandSHIFT-G is managed with no/reduced tillage management and the remainder is managed with conventional tillage. As we assume that differences in crop yields between conventional and no-till management are negligible (Yue et al., 2023), s_{nt} is also the share in the crops production. The area extent of these sub-systems is passed to LPJ-GUESS, which applies different tillage factor to model turnover of soil carbon.

3.3.2 Agroforestry LMT

The effect of agroforestry on carbon fluxes is modelled based on the concept of the land equivalent ratio (Mead and Willey, 1980). In an agricultural system producing two crops A and B on the same land, the land equivalent ratio is defined as:

$$L = L_A + L_B = \frac{Y_A}{Y'_A} + \frac{Y_B}{Y'_B} \quad (1)$$

with L_A and L_B being the land equivalent of the crops A and B, Y being the yield in the intercropping system and Y' the yield in a sole crop system. Thus, the land equivalent ratio is the relative area as sole crops needed to produce the same amount of crops in the intercropping system.

In our coupled model system, an agroforestry system is represented as an intercropping system consisting of a primary crop and trees. A country-level demand of production is only defined for the primary crop, while the accumulation of biomass in the trees represents carbon sequestration as a side effect. If LandSHIFT-G allocated an area a' to meet a given production of a crop in sole crop cultivation, the area a of the agroforestry system needed to produce the same amount of crop was a'/L_{crop} . Hence, with values of $L_{crop} < 1$ a conversion of the sole crop system into agroforestry leads to a larger extent of agricultural area. However, additional carbon is accumulated in the tree biomass, which we assume equal to the carbon accumulation in a natural stand on an area equivalent to $a_{tree} = a L_{tree}$.

If a share s_{AF} of the production of a crop is accomplished in agroforestry systems and the rest in sole crop cultivation, the average (effective) land equivalent ratio representative for the country-wide production system is given as:

$$\bar{L} = \bar{L}_{crop} + \bar{L}_{tree} \quad (2)$$

with

$$\bar{L}_{crop} = 1 - s_{AF} + s_{AF}L_{crop} \quad (3)$$

and

$$\bar{L}_{tree} = s_{AF}L_{tree}. \quad (4)$$

The inputs to the coupled model system are given as time series of \bar{L}_{tree} and \bar{L}_{crop} .

3.3.3 *Afforestation/Reforestation LMT (natural development of vegetation)*

Afforestation is represented in the model system by the spatial allocation of newly established forests (in theory, as LPJG-GUESS may grow other types of vegetation depending on climate conditions) on as many grid cells as needed to fulfill a prescribed area to be afforested in each time step and country. During land-use allocation, afforestation has lower priority than urban area, irrigated and rain-fed cropland and pasture. In order to avoid that afforestation converts natural vegetation into afforested area, a constraint in LandSHIFT-G is used that only allows afforestation to be allocated on grid cells that were previously crop or pasture. An optimization has been introduced by selecting areas for afforestation with the highest potential for carbon sequestration, as given by a potential vegetation simulation using EC-Earth3-CC.

The aggregated area of new afforested stands per grid cell of EC-Earth-CC is added to existing natural area and the sum is passed to LPG-GUESS (either transition type “pasture-to-nature” or “cropland-to-nature”). LPJ-GUESS starts to simulate growth of a forest stand established by natural succession, altering carbon fluxes and, hence, climate as modelled by EC-Earth3-CC.

A major simplification and limitation of the representation of afforestation in the modelling system is that it cannot simulate the active planting of trees, e.g., by forest managers, which in practice accelerates initial forest growth. Hence, the mitigation potential until a given point in time might be underestimated.

The required model input for the LMT afforestation are time series of afforested area by country.

3.3.4 *Bioenergy production in combination with carbon capture and storage (BECCS LMT and PyCCS LMT)*

The combination of bioenergy production and different methods of carbon capture and storage (CCS) potentially provides two mechanisms of climate change mitigation. Firstly, it can avoid emissions if power generation from renewable bioenergy feedstock, which is almost carbon neutral, substitutes energy from fossil fuels. Secondly, it may constitute a net sink of atmospheric carbon, as a fraction of the carbon sequestered in the feedstock is ultimately converted into relatively stable forms of carbon so it is prevented from being re-emitted to the atmosphere as carbon dioxide.

In the coupled model system, growth of the bioenergy feedstock and related carbon fluxes from atmosphere to biomass are simulated by LPJ-GUESS. The model transfers a fraction of the carbon stored in the biomass to a carbon pool with a (very) low decomposition rate, instead of assuming

that the carbon in the biomass is released back to the atmosphere after harvest, leading to a net flux of atmospheric carbon to that pool. Further, anthropogenic emissions, which are an external input to EC-Earth3-CC, are reduced by the avoided emissions from fossil fuels equivalent to the bioenergy production.

The model supports the representation of two LMTs related to bioenergy production based on purpose grown bioenergy crops as a feedstock:

- Bioenergy production with carbon capture and storage in geological structures (BECCS) and
- Carbon storage in form of biochar from pyrolysis buried in agricultural soils with production of bioenergy/biofuels as a side product (PyCCS).

Moreover, the model can represent bioenergy/biofuels without carbon capture and storage (BE), which actually constitutes an LMT. However, BE was not addressed in the scenario development as it is already widely adopted (reference scenario) and has zero potential of actual CDR. In general, all three LMTs are controlled by two uniformly applied parameters specifying the conversion efficiency of feedstock carbon into stored carbon and avoided emissions from fossil fuels per mass unit of carbon in the feedstock. The parameter values were estimated based on conversion rates of BECCS systems in Merfort et al. (2023), mass and energy distribution to bio-char, bio-oil and gases with the pyrolysis of miscanthus (Conrad et al., 2019) and a carbon emission intensity of diesel fuel (Umweltbundesamt, 2022) (Table 3). Diesel fuel with a rather low carbon intensity (74 kg CO₂/TJ) compared to coal (~94 kg CO₂/TJ) was used as a proxy of fossil fuels to be replaced in order to avoid overestimation of the substitution effect given the ongoing de-carbonization of the energy sector. Further, the liquid phase of pyrolysis products (bio-oil) is likely to substitute liquid fossil fuels where electrification is not possible, e.g. in the transport, navigation, and aviation sectors.

Table 3 Parameters of carbon conversion efficiency and avoided emission for LMTs related to bioenergy production.

LMT	Carbon conversion efficiency (%)	Avoided emissions (kg C/kg C _{feedstock})
BE	0	0.37
BECCS	62	0.35
PyCCS	40	0.22

Further, the interplay of following input time series, specified by crop and country, controls the area used for the three LMTs:

- Crop production (P)
- Share of crop area used for bioenergy feedstock production (s_{BE})
- Fraction of bioenergy feedstock used for BECCS (f_{BECCS})
- Fraction of bioenergy feedstock used for PyCCS (f_{PyCCS})

According to this, the bioenergy production P_{BE} in each grid cell is given by the product of P and S_{BE} , the feedstock available for BECCS is given by the product of P_{BE} and f_{BECCS} , while the feedstock for PyCCS is given by the product of P_{BE} and f_{PyCCS} . The remainder of P_{BE} is used as the feedstock for BE.

For PyCCS, this model representation does not cover potential secondary climate mitigation effects of biochar application to soils. These effects arise because application of biochar might improve soils, leading to higher yields and increased resilience to droughts (improved water holding capacity) of food production systems and, ultimately, less emissions from land-use change (Majumder et al., 2019).

4 Methodology - Quantification of LMT scaling scenarios

In the framework of LANDMARC, LandSHIFT-G is set-up to model land-use change on a 5 arc-minute raster with input data on country level. Hence, the model relies on a comprehensive input dataset with global coverage on country level. The dataset comprises time series (in 5-year time steps) of population, crop production (5 crop types, both rain-fed and irrigated, one rain-fed 2nd generation bioenergy crop), technological change in crop yields, and livestock production to determine the context of the agricultural sector, in which the deployment of various LMT portfolios takes place. In addition, input time series controlling the LMTs are also needed on the country level. Due to the complexity of the global agricultural system, a dataset consistently integrating regional demand, regional production and global trade of agricultural commodities for a scenario must be used. Further, the global dynamics of the production of food and bio-based materials is strongly connected to the energy sector via bioenergy demand and production. Therefore, we relied on results of the Integrated Assessment Model (IAM) MESSAGE-GLOBIOM, which provides a consistent representation of the agricultural and energy sectors (GEA, 2012; Havlík et al., 2011; Messner and Strubegger, 1995) and are publicly available².

In a multi-model experiment studying the implication of the Shared Socioeconomic Pathways for energy, land-use, and greenhouse gas emissions, the scenarios were analyzed with several IAMs. The results of MESSAGE-GLOBIOM were identified as the marker scenario for SSP2 because this model is particularly well suited to model the aspects most important under SSP2 (Fricko et al., 2017; Riahi et al., 2017). MESSAGE-GLOBIOM was used to model SSP2 (besides other SSPs) combined with assumptions on the implementation of climate policies, including in the land-use sector, that lead to climate mitigation required to be consistent with various Representative Concentration Pathways (SSP, van Vuuren et al., 2011) (Bauer et al., 2017; Popp et al., 2017; Rogelj et al., 2018). Thus, those projections form a suitable basis to derive input data for LandSHIFT-G specifying the evolution of the agricultural sector providing the context for the LMT scaling scenarios. The reference scenario is represented by results of SSP2-RCP4.5 (~2.7° warming), the “*Moderate CDR Ambition*” scenario is

² <https://tntcat.iiasa.ac.at/SspDb/dsd?Action=htmlpage&page=welcome>

represented by results of SSP2-RCP2.6 (~2° warming); the “*High CDR Ambition*”-scenario (~1.5° warming) is represented by results of SSP2-RCP1.9 (Rogelj et al., 2018). Unfortunately, the available data from MESSAGE-GLOBIOM does not include the underlying technological yield change of crops and the sub-fractions of cropland area used for the production of food, feed, and bio-based materials (FFM) and bioenergy production (BE). However, we were able to estimate the missing information based on suitable assumptions as explained in section 4.1 while additional assumptions defining the deployment of LMTs are given in 4.2.

The purpose of simulating the “*Reference*” scenario is to generate model output for a SSP2-RCP4.5 scenario in which LMTs are deployed only to an extent already implemented or planned to be implemented according to legally binding policies. As stated, the reference scenario was established from the beginning of the project in order to be able to re-use existing basic model inputs and to keep the findings from the modelling experiments in WP7 easily comparable to other work in the climate modelling community. The inputs are taken directly from the LUH2 dataset for SSP2-RCP4.5 (Hurtt et al., 2020). Furthermore, the model was operated without deployment the newly implemented representation of LMTs. However, we became aware of an inconsistency of the LUH2 dataset and the model outcomes of MESSAGE-GLOBIOM with respect to production of bioenergy during the revisions of the input dataset. While in LUH2, the production and area of bioenergy crops stays more or less constant on a very low level it actually grows in the MESSAGE-GLOBIOM results. Thus, we prepared an updated input dataset for a SSP2-RCP4.5 scenario, hereafter referred to as “*Corrected Reference*”, with bioenergy being produced according to MESSAGE-GLOBIOM (1st generation only), assuming 50% PyCCS for the CCS share in OECD countries, China, and India and 100% PyCCS in the rest of the world. Bioenergy, PyCCS and BECCS, however, are the only LMTs considered in this “*Corrected Reference*” scenario as these were affected by the inconsistencies between LUH2 and MESSAGE-GLOBIOM (no deployment of the remaining LMTs as in the original reference scenario).

4.1 Derivation of basic input data for the land-use model

For the derivation of future changes in cropland and pasture area, relative changes in these variables informed by results from MESSAGE-GLOBIOM for 5 world regions were combined with absolute data derived from the LUH2 dataset representing SSP2-RCP4.5 (Hurtt et al., 2020). The LUH2 dataset was chosen as reference case as it provides spatially distributed cropland and pasture area and differentiates five crop classes in rain-fed and irrigation management. Further, this choice will promote the comparison of our results to other studies by the climate modelling community (Eyring et al., 2016) due to harmonized assumptions on land-use change.

The approach included the calculation of following scaling factors from MESSAGE-GLOBIOM output on a regional level (see 4.1.1):

- The fraction of cropland area for the production of FFM in total cropland (s_{FFM}) in the base year 2015;
- the fraction of cropland for 1st generation bioenergy crops (BE1) in total cropland (s_{BE1}) in the base year 2015;
- the change factor of cropland area for food, feed, and bio-based materials relative to the value in 2015 (α_{FFM});
- the change factor of cropland area for 1st generation bioenergy crops relative to the value in 2015 (α_{BE1});
- the ratio of pasture area in a given scenario to pasture area in the reference scenario (ρ_{PA}); and
- the ratio of total cropland in a given scenario to total cropland in the reference scenario (ρ_{tot}).

Note that α_{FFM} , α_{BE1} , ρ_{PA} and ρ_{tot} are defined as a function of time.

In a subsequent downscaling step, cropping area in the LMT scaling scenarios with the exception of 2nd generation bioenergy crops (BE2) were projected by multiplying the country-level absolute values of cropland area for food, feed and bio-based materials (FFM) and BE1 in 2015, as given for the reference scenario derived from LUH2, with α_{FFM} and α_{BE1} , respectively (see 4.1.2).

Figure 1 Illustration of the approach to calculate area for 2nd generation bioenergy crops and afforestation. Examples 1-4 compared to the absolute values from LUH2 used as the reference.

In addition, total cropland area and pasture area in a LMT scaling scenario were computed as the time series values of the reference scenario multiplied by ρ_{tot} and ρ_{PA} , respectively (Figure 1). In a

scenario with higher CDR ambitions, this leads to an expansion of total cropland compared to the reference case (with only little LMT deployment) (Example 2 in Figure 1). However, a large fraction of future cropland will be used for the production of bioenergy on newly established stands of 2nd generation BE crops, which may provide a mitigation effect through avoided emissions from fossil fuels and potentially negative emissions due to carbon capture and storage. Future cropland area for the production of 2nd generation bioenergy crops results in the difference of projected total cropland area and the cropland area for FFM and BE1. Cropland expansion can compensate projected reductions in pasture area (Example 3 in Figure 1). However, if total agricultural area (crops and pasture) are lower than in the base year 2015 the freed pasture area can be used for afforestation (Example 4 in Figure 1).

Ultimately, the derived input data in terms of pasture and cropland area had to be converted into corresponding time series of agricultural production (see 4.1.3). This was necessary because the feedback loops between the LandSHIFT-G and EC-Earth-CC, which are realized via crop yields and pasture productivity as modelled by LPJ-GUESS, only work if LandSHIFT-G is driven by demand of production. In this case, climate change leading to changes in crop yields or pasture productivity will cause changes in the required agricultural area. Depending on the direction of change, this either may lead to additional (lower yields/productivity) or avoided (higher yields/productivity) deforestation.

In order to solve the equations and to deal with limitations of the coupled model system, a number of assumptions had to be made by the researchers responsible for Task 6.4:

1. In the base year 2015, average yields of bioenergy crops (whole plant harvest) are a factor of two higher than average yields of food crops (50 % of the plant biomass harvested, i.e. harvest index 0.5 as a reasonable estimate for grains (e.g., Yang and Zhang, 2010)), irrespective of the location, i.e. the yield ratio $\rho_y=1/2$. (Note: this assumption was replaced in the revised calculations, see 4.1.1)
2. The production of 2nd generation bioenergy crops in the reference scenario (SSP2-RCP4.5) is negligible as growing 2nd generation bioenergy is connected to LMTs only deployed in the LMT scaling scenarios. Hence, total cropland in the reference comprises area for FFM and 1st generation bioenergy crops.
3. We assumed the cropland area of 1st generation bioenergy crops to stay constant at the extent of 2015. This is in line with the LUH2 dataset where bioenergy crops cover about ~5% of cropland in 2015 and show little dynamics. (Note: This assumption was replaced in the revision of the input dataset, see 4.1.1)
4. The cropland area of 1st generation bioenergy crops is identical in the reference and LMT scaling scenarios. Differences in cropland or crop production for BE between scenarios are due to the cultivation of 2nd generation bioenergy crops.
5. Technological change factor of crop yields for FFM (τ_{FFM} , see 4.1.1 equation 10) were assumed to be the same in all scenarios as those were considered optimistic already in the reference scenario and improvements in scenarios with higher ambitions of climate mitigation seemed unlikely (expert guess confirmed by stakeholders).

6. The technological change factors for crops yields (τ_{FFM}) must not exceed a value of 2.5 to avoid unreasonable values resulting from the calculations explained in section 4.1.1 (max 150% yield improvement).
7. Relative changes estimated for a region are equally valid in each country in the region and also for each crop within the countries.

4.1.1 Regional relative changes in the agricultural sector

Output from MESSAGE-GLOBIOM was available for the following five regional aggregations of the world (Table 4, see Annex A for a listing of individual countries covered by LandSHIFT-G):

Table 4 Spatial aggregation of the five region aggregation level (MESSAGE model)

Code of 5-region level aggregate (MESSAGE) ³	Description
R5.2ASIA	Most Asian countries with the exception of the Middle East, Japan and Former Soviet Union states
R5.2LAM	Countries of Latin America and the Caribbean
R5.2MAF	Countries of the Middle East and Africa
R5.2OECD	Countries of OECD 90 and EU member states and candidates
R5.2REF	Countries from the Reforming Economies of Eastern Europe and the Former Soviet Union

For SSP2-RCP4.5, SSP2-RCP2.6, and SSP2-RCP1.9 MESSAGE-GLOBIOM provides, amongst others, time series of the following state variables by region:

P_{BE} Production of bioenergy crops (variable “Agricultural Production|Crops|Energy”);

P_{FFM} Production of non-energy crops (food, feed and bio-materials) (variable “Agricultural Production|Crops|Non-Energy”);

A_{tot} (physical) Cropland area (taken as physical area) (variable “Land Cover|Cropland”);

A_{PA} (physical) Pasture area (taken as physical area) (variable “Land Cover|Pasture”).

From results for the reference scenario, we compute the technological change factor of crop yields for FFM, and the base-year values of cropland area for FFM and BE (=BE1), which will also be used for all LMT scaling scenarios. Based on assumption 1, the total cropland area in 2015 is split into cropland area for FFM (A_{FFM}) and cropland area for bioenergy crops (A_{BE}) according to

$$A_{FFM}(2015) = \frac{P_{FFM}(2015)}{P_{FFM}(2015) + \rho_y P_{BE}(2015)} A_{tot}(2015) \quad (5)$$

³ <https://tntcat.iiasa.ac.at/SspDb/dsd?Action=htmlpage&page=10#regiondefs>

and

$$A_{BE}(2015) = \frac{\rho_y P_{BE}(2015)}{P_{FFM}(2015) + \rho_y P_{BE}(2015)} A_{tot}(2015), \quad (6)$$

with $A_{tot}(t)$ given as

$$A_{tot}(t) = A_{FFM}(t) + A_{BE}(t) = A_{FFM}(t) + A_{BE1}(t) + A_{BE2}(t). \quad (7)$$

From assumptions 2, 3, and 4 follows that the area of 1st generation bioenergy crops at time t , which is valid in all scenarios, is given as

$$A_{BE1}(t) = A_{BE}(2015). \quad (8)$$

Based on equation (3) and assumption 2 cropland area for non-energy crops in the reference scenario is given as

$$A_{FFM}(t) = A_{tot}(t) - A_{BE1}(t). \quad (9)$$

Thus we can calculate of the technological yield change factor of non-energy crops at time t as

$$\tau_{FFM}(t) = \frac{Y_{FFM}(t)}{Y_{FFM}(2015)} = \frac{\frac{P_{FFM}(t)}{A_{FFM}(t)}}{\frac{P_{FFM}(2015)}{A_{FFM}(2015)}} = \frac{P_{FFM}(t)A_{FFM}(2015)}{P_{FFM}(2015)A_{FFM}(t)}, \quad (10)$$

where the average yield of crops for food, feed, and bio-materials Y_{FFM} at time t defined as

$$Y_{FFM}(t) = \frac{P_{FFM}(t)}{A_{FFM}(t)}. \quad (11)$$

In a second step, data from MESSAGE-GLOBIOM for SSP2 combined with a different RCP (i.e. SSP2-RCP2.6 or SSP2-RCP1.9) and previously calculated variables taken from the reference scenario (indicated by a prime symbol, e.g. A'_{BE1}) the missing time series for the LMT scaling scenarios were calculated as follows. Note that all scenarios have a common starting point for the base year 2015.

According to assumption 4 cropland area of 1st generation bioenergy crops is given as

$$A_{BE1}(t) = A'_{BE1}(t). \quad (12)$$

As A_{BE1} is constant over time (assumption 3) its change factor with respect to the base-year value $\alpha_{BE1}(t)=1$, while, according to assumption 5, the change factor of A_{FFM} can be calculated as

$$\alpha_{FFM}(t) = \frac{\pi_{FFM}(t)}{\tau'_{FFM}(t)}, \quad (13)$$

where $\pi_{FFM}(t)$ is the change factor of production of crops for food, feed, and bio-based materials defined as

$$\pi_{FFM}(t) = P_{FFM}(t) / P_{FFM}(2015). \quad (14)$$

Finally, we calculated the ratios of A_{tot} and A_{PA} to their values in the reference scenario as

$$\rho_{tot}(t) = \frac{A_{tot}(t)}{A'_{tot}(t)} \quad (15)$$

and

$$\rho_{PA}(t) = \frac{A_{PA}(t)}{A'_{PA}(t)}, \quad (16)$$

which were used in the downscaling step to adjust the corresponding variables on country level in the LMT scaling scenario.

During the revision of the LMT scaling scenarios after the regional workshops, additional information on MESSAGE- GLOBIOM results (readings from graphs in Supplementary Information of Fricko et al. (2017)) could be used to improve important assumptions. Firstly, assumption 1, the yield ratio of food and bioenergy crops (previously $\rho_y=1/2$) was changed to $\rho_y=1/5$. Secondly, assumption 3 (constant 1st generation bioenergy production) was replaced by the weaker assumption that yields of bioenergy crops do not change due to factor inputs (e.g. fertilizer input, irrigation, management) as this would lead to inconsistencies in the carbon balances computed by LPJ-GUESS.

Hence, the calculation of cropland area of 1st generation bioenergy crops was revised to

$$\alpha_{BE1}(t) = \frac{P_{BE}(t)}{P'_{BE}(2015)}. \quad (17)$$

4.1.2 *Downscaling of regional changes to country level*

The downscaling of regional relative changes in agricultural areas, as compared to the base year, in a LMT scaling scenario was based on the initial values absolute in 2015 from the reference scenario. In the following, we describe the calculation steps per region. Each country belongs entirely to one of the five world regions.

The input dataset to LandSHIFT-G for the reference scenario consists of the time series for each country in 5-year time steps, which were calculated from LUH2 data for SSP2-RCP4.5 aggregated to country level. The aggregation of agricultural area in a country by type (crop or pasture) for the reference was done according to

$$A'_{ij}(t) = \sum_c a(t)_{ci} S_{cj}, \quad (18)$$

with area a allocated to type i (pasture or crops) in a grid cell c , in which a share s of the grid cell area belongs to country j . A'_{ij} for crops were separated into the portions for FFM and BE1 analogous to equations (1) and (2) but with the crop-specific area instead of total cropland.

Thus, scenario projections of A_{FFM} and A_{BE1} for all countries j in a region were calculated based on the regional change factors as

$$A_{FFM,ij}(t) = \alpha_{FFM}(t)A'_{FFM,ij}(2015) \quad (19)$$

and

$$A_{BE1,ij}(t) = \alpha_{BE1}(t)A'_{BE1,ij}(2015). \quad (20)$$

The cropland area of 2nd generation bioenergy crops A_{BE2} , which is zero in 2015, had to be derived in a different way. We calculated the extent of total cropland including A_{BE2} as

$$A_{tot,j}(t) = \rho_{tot}A'_{tot,j}(t) \quad (21)$$

and defined the cropland area of 2nd generation bioenergy crops as

$$A_{BE2}(t) = A_{tot,j}(t) - \sum_i \{A_{FFM,ij}(t) + A_{BE1,ij}(t)\}. \quad (22)$$

Note we assumed zero cropping area of 2nd generation bioenergy crops in the reference value $A'_{tot,j}(t)$ (*assumption 2*).

Finally, pasture area in a country j was calculated as

$$A_{PA,j}(t) = \rho_{PA}(t)A'_{PA,j}(2015). \quad (23)$$

4.1.3 Conversion of projection of agricultural area into production

Input data as calculated according to 4.1.1 and 4.1.2 in terms of area where used for intermediate simulation runs with stand-alone LandSHIFT-G configured to use area as a driver. The simulations used projections of potential crop yields and pasture productivity from LPJ-GUESS based on climate data from an EC-Earth3-CC run using SSP2-RCP4.5 climate forcings (Eyring et al., 2016) and input data on agricultural development in terms of area representing SSP2-RCP2.6 and SSP2-RCP1.9 (see 4.1.1 and 4.1.2). From the resulting allocation pattern of the various crops and pasture and spatially distributed potential yields y (or grassland net primary productivity for pastures) from LPJ-GUESS, the production by type i (pasture or crops) in a country j was calculated for each scenario as

$$P_{ij} = \sum_c a_{ci}y_{ci}s_{cj}, \quad (24)$$

with area a in a grid cell c , in which a share s of the grid cell area belongs to country j .

For the preliminary and final simulation runs with the couple model system, time series of production were used as input.

4.2 Input data for EC-Earth-CC

For all simulation runs with the coupled model, input data for EC-Earth-CC (see section 3.2) were the same as for the selected reference scenario, i.e. SSP2-RCP4.5, taken from the CMIP6 project (Eyring et al., 2016), which are publicly available.

4.3 Input data on the deployment of LMTs

In the following sections, we explain the considerations and assumptions made to prepare quantitative model inputs controlling the deployment of LMTs in the scenario simulations. For each LMT we first present the preliminary settings used for the simulation runs presented to stakeholders at the regional workshops of WP6 (see D6.2) and, second, explain how assumptions or settings were revised after the workshops. The revisions were mostly done to address stakeholder feedback but were also complemented with considerations of the researchers responsible for Task 6.4, aiming at the maximization of inter-scenario differences within reasonable bounds. If the assumption are based on literature or stakeholder feedback, it is referenced accordingly.

4.3.1 *No/reduced tillage LMT*

The representation of the LMT “no tillage” was controlled by the share of annual crops produced under no-tillage management s_{nt} as a function of time and country. For the preliminary model input, we assumed a uniform target $s_{nt, target}$ -value in each country and that the target was reached in the target year (y_t). The initial share of cropland managed without tillage in 2015 ($s_{nt, init}$) varied across countries (see below) and, hence, affected the potentials of climate mitigation through this LMT in individual countries. For each country, we specified the time series of s_{nt} as the linear interpolation between the three nodes $s_{nt}(2015) = s_{nt, init}$ in the base year, $s_{nt}(y_t) = s_{nt, target}$ in the target year, and $s_{nt}(2100) = s_{nt, target}$ at the end of the century. For perennial crops (CC3per, CC3peri, CC4per, CC4peri) we assumed $s_{nt} = 0$ in all time steps.

We calculated the initial value of s_{nt} in each country based on a spatially distributed (5 arc-minute resolution) dataset on tillage representing the conditions around the year 2005 (Porwollik et al., 2018; Porwollik et al., 2019). For 42 different crops, this dataset provides maps of the type of tillage system likely used for the cultivation of the crop. Out of the six types of tillage systems conventional annual tillage, rotational tillage, traditional annual tillage, traditional rotational tillage, reduced tillage, and conservation agriculture we assumed that reduced tillage and conservation agriculture were representative for the reduced/no-tillage LMT. We calculated the share of crops grown with reduced/no-tillage in the total number of crops grown in a given grid cell from Porwollik et al. (2018). This share was interpreted to be the fraction of cropland area in a grid cell that is managed with reduced/no-tillage. It was aggregated to an estimate of initial s_{nt} -values ($s_{nt, init}$) on country level by calculation of weighted average using the gridded cropping area as allocated by LandSHIFT-G in the base year 2015 as a weighting factor. This analysis was done separately for each annual crop type in

the coupled model (C3 annual, C4 annual, C3 N-fixing) considering a subset of crops according to the mapping in Table 5. The complete list of initial values for all countries is given in Annex B.

Table 5 Mapping of annual crop types in the coupled model system to crops in Porwollik et al. 2018, crop codes in parenthesis

Crop in coupled model system	Crops in Porwollik et al. 2018
Annual C3 crops (CC3ann, CC3anni)	wheat (whea), rice (rice), barley (barl), potato (pota), sweet potato (swpo), yams (yams), cassava (cass), chickpea (chick), coconut (cnut), sunflower (sunf), sesame seed (sesa), sugar beet (sugb), cotton (cott), tobacco (toba), other cereals (ocer), other roots (orts), rapeseed (rape), other oilseeds (ooil), other fibers (ofib), vegetables (vege), and crops summarized under “rest”
Annual C4 crops (CC4ann, CC4anni)	maize (maiz), pearl millet (pmil), and small millet (smil)
N-fixing C3 crops (CC3nfx/CC3nfxi)	bean (bean), cowpea (cowp), pigeonpea (pige), lentil (lent), soybean (soyb), groundnut (grou), and other pulses (opul)

In the preliminary input data, we assumed a target value 2/3 of the cropland under annual crops to be managed with reduced/no-tillage, which corresponds to a doubling of the highest initial values (99% quantile as a robust estimate of the maximum) found for all crops and countries (see Table A 2 in Annex B). Starting from the country-specific initial value the target was reached in 2100 in the “Moderate CDR Ambition” and in 2050 in the High Ambition scenario. These assumptions were equal for all countries.

At the regional stakeholder workshops of WP6 (see D6.2), in particular in the European case, participants highlighted the importance of no-tillage, in combination with year-round cover crops, for increasing soil carbon storage. However, it was stressed that conditions for adoption of no-tillage practices are highly variable across countries. Hence, we revised the assumption and split countries into two groups. Higher income countries (OECD), countries already experienced in no-till management (Latin America) and single large economies in other regions (China and India) were assumed to reach the target significantly earlier (in 2050) than the remaining countries. This is because it is easier for farmers in high-income countries to cope with the relatively high costs of a conversion from conventional to no-till practices. Furthermore, it takes time to organize the knowledge transfer to countries less experienced in no-till farming. In addition to changed dynamics of the input time series, the target value was increased for all countries to be 100% of the cropland (annual crops) in “High CDR Ambition”.

Table 6 provides a comparison of the preliminary and final assumptions of all settings for the reduced/no-till LMT.

Table 6 Summary of assumptions on LMT reduced/no-tillage for the “Reference”, the “Corrected Reference” (SSP2-RCP4.5), and the LMT scaling scenarios, highlighting the changes between preliminary assumptions and final assumption after revision. Note: No revision of input data for “Reference”; no preliminary runs for “Corrected Reference” (SSP2-RCP4.5).

Scenario	Region	Parameter	Preliminary assumption	Final assumption
Reference	global	$S_{nt, target}$	0	-
		target year	2015	-
SSP2-RCP4.5_v2	global	$S_{nt, target}$	-	$S_{nt, init}$
		target year	-	2015
Moderate CDR Ambition	OECD + LAM + CN + IN	$S_{nt, target}$	0.67	0.67
		target year	2100	2050
	remaining countries	$S_{nt, target}$	0.67	0.67
		target year	2100	2100
High CDR Ambition	OECD + LAM + CN + IN	$S_{nt, target}$	0.67	1.0
		target year	2050	2050
	remaining countries	$S_{nt, target}$	0.67	1.0
		target year	2050	2100

4.3.2 Agroforestry LMT

For the preliminary model simulations, researchers made very simple assumptions representing a gradual conversion from sole crop cultivation to agroforestry systems for the production of all crops and from pasture to silvopasture (integration of livestock production and trees). We set $L_{crop}=1$ and, thus, $\bar{L}_{crop} = 1$, for both scenarios, all countries, and all time steps. Hence, we assumed that the beneficial effects of agroforestry, such as avoided heat stress of crops or less evaporation losses from soils due to shading trees, help maintain the yields of sole crops although the cropping area is partly used for growing trees. The average land equivalent ratio of trees was interpolated linearly between $\bar{L}_{tree}(2015) = 0$ and $\bar{L}_{tree}(2100) = 0.25$ in all countries. This can be interpreted as zero agroforestry share in 2015 and a gradual conversion to 100% agroforestry in 2100, where the typical agroforestry or silvopasture system has a total land equivalent ratio of 1.25 ($L_{crop}=1.0$ and $L_{tree}=0.25$) (Table 8).

At the ACTO regional workshop of WP6 (see D6.2), participants pointed out it that the yield of the crop in agroforestry systems is lower than in sole crop cultivation. Consequently, the production of the same amount of crops needs more area when done in agroforestry, taking away area potentially available for other LMTs (e.g. BECCS) or, in the worst case, leading to the conversion of natural vegetation to cropland due to indirect land-use change. The enhanced carbon sequestration in woody biomass as compared to cropland will likely not compensate for the carbon emissions caused by such effects. Thus, agroforestry is in fact not a land-use base mitigation technology. However, workshop participants stressed that agroforestry potentially offers many advantages over sole crop cultivation and must be considered an important measure for climate adaptation and for mitigating biodiversity loss. The advantages discussed include provision of additional income possibilities (non-timber forest products), improved resilience to droughts, reduced soil erosion, and higher biodiversity which is also supported by literature (e.g., Sollen-Norrin et al., 2020).

The assumptions on land equivalent ratio used for modelling agroforestry were also revised based on findings in the literature. In summary, we found information on a large number of different agroforestry systems, each to be applied under different environmental conditions and with highly variable land equivalent ratios (e.g. Nair et al. (2021) and Shi et al. (2018)). Hence, representing the mix of different systems by a single “average” or “typical” system, which is currently a requirement of the coupled model, is highly uncertain. Nevertheless, we used selected observations in a systematic database of experimental data on intercropping and agroforestry systems (Paut et al., 2023; Paut et al., 2024) to inform the model parameters. In a first step, we categorized all countries into rough climate zones (educated guess) mainly characterized by “dry”, “wet”, and “tropical” conditions and a class “mixed” for countries stretching across several climate zones. In a second step, we selected all observations of agroforestry systems combining one (non-tree) crop and tree species from Paut et al. (2024), and calculated average land equivalent ratio of those systems stratified by Köppen-Geiger climate zones according to Peel et al. (2007). From those findings, we made an estimate of land equivalent ratios representative for agroforestry systems applied in the roughly defined climate zone as given in Table 7. For Silvopasture we assumed that there are no adverse effects on net primary production (NPP) of grass or forage if tree cover does not exceed a value representative for $L_{tree}=0.4$.

Table 7 Revised estimates of the representative land equivalent ratio assumed for agroforestry and silvopasture systems differentiated according to the dominant climate conditions.
AF=Agroforestry, SP=silvopasture

Dominant climate in Country	Type	Description	L_{crop}	L_{trees}	L
tropical	AF	average of findings for Köppen-Geiger zones “Af - tropical wet” and “Aw -tropical wet and dry”	0.77	1.00	1.77
wet	AF	findings for zone “Cfb – marine”	0.44	0.83	1.27
dry	AF	findings for zone “Csa – Mediterranean”	0.69	1.00	1.69
mixed	AF	intermediate between wet and dry, matching the findings of zone “Aw”	0.55	1.00	1.55
all	SP	no NPP reductions for grass at a tree cover representative for $L_{tree}=0.4$	1.00	0.40	1.00

The model drivers for the LMT agroforestry, \bar{L}_{crop} and \bar{L}_{tree} , were computed according to equations (3) and (4) based on assumption on S_{AF} (Table 8).

Guided by the notion that the scenario “High CDR Ambition” is characterized by a focus on high-tech solutions that require a large-scale technological implementation (e.g. BECCS), which is fostered by a strong regional engagement, we assume that agroforestry is deployed only to very limited extent. This is because agroforestry may lead to an expansion of cropland for food production, which would narrow the possibilities of, e.g., bioenergy production with CCS. Further, we differentiate between two groups of countries (Table 8). The first group are countries with high income (OECD), a highly mechanized agricultural sector (REF), or single large economies with rather high potential to

implement large-scale LMT solutions (CN and IN). The remaining countries are in the second group. For the first group, we assume less deployment of agroforestry, i.e. 15% of the cropland in 2100, as those countries focus on other LMTs whereas agroforestry covers a slightly higher share of cropland in the remaining countries, reaching 20% in 2100.

Table 8 Summary of assumptions made for the LMT agroforestry in the “Reference”, “Corrected Reference” (SSP2-RCP4.5) and the LMT scaling scenarios, comparing preliminary and final settings. AF=agroforestry (with a crop), SP=silvopasture. Note: No revision of input data for “Reference”; no preliminary runs for “Corrected Reference” (SSP2-RCP4.5).

Scenario	Region	Parameter	Preliminary assumption	Final assumption
Reference	global	$S_{AF}(AF)$	0	-
		$S_{AF}(SP)$	0	-
		L, L_{crop}, L_{tree}	-	see Table 7-
Corrected Reference	global	$S_{AF}(AF)$	-	0
		$S_{AF}(SP)$	-	0
		L, L_{crop}, L_{tree}	-	-
Moderate CDR Ambition	global	$S_{AF}(AF)$	0 (2015) 1 (2100)	0 (2015) 0.4 (2100)
		$S_{AF}(SP)$	0 (2015) 1 (2100)	0 (2015) 0.35 (2100)
		L, L_{crop}, L_{tree}	$L_{crop}=1,$ $L_{tree}=0.25$	see Table 7-
High CDR Ambition	OECD + REF + CN + IN	$S_{AF}(AF)$	0 (2015) 1 (2100)	0 (2015) 0.15 (2100)
		$S_{AF}(SP)$	0 (2015) 1 (2100)	0 (2015) 0.7 (2100)
		L, L_{crop}, L_{tree}	$L_{crop}=1,$ $L_{tree}=0.25$	see Table 7-
	remaining countries	$S_{AF}(AF)$	0 (2015) 1 (2100)	0 (2015) 0.2 (2100)
		$S_{AF}(SP)$	0 (2015) 1 (2100)	0 (2015) 0.7 (2100)
		L, L_{crop}, L_{tree}	$L_{crop}=1,$ $L_{tree}=0.25$	see Table 7-

4.3.3 Afforestation/Reforestation LMT

For both scenarios, the input data for afforestation follows directly from the calculation described in the sections 4.1.1 and 4.1.2. The afforested area is calculated as the area freed from pasture minus the expansion of cropland as compared to the base year. If the result is negative (cropland expansion is larger than the reduction in pasture area), afforestation is zero.

For the scenario “High CDR Ambition”, the MESSAGE-GLOBIOM results (SSP2-RCP1.9) show a relatively strong reduction in the area of pasture and cropland for food, which is not compensated by the increase in cropland for bioenergy. This results in ~650 mill. ha of afforestation globally (2100). In contrast, afforestation in “Moderate CDR Ambition” is negligible in the global context because

reductions in pasture land and cropland for food are less pronounced and mostly compensated by the expansion of bioenergy cropland.

4.3.4 BECCS LMT and PyCCS LMT

The share of cropland area of FFM crops used for the production of bioenergy feedstock (s_{BE}) was calculated from the ratio of A_{BE1} to the sum of A_{BE1} and A_{FFM} . Further, the output of MESSAGE-GLOBIOM provides variables from which the fraction of bioenergy feedstock used for BECCS can be calculated as:

$$f_{BECCS}^* = \frac{E_{PBECCS} + E_{SBECCS}}{E_{PBE} + E_{SBE}}, \quad (25)$$

with:

E_{PBE}	Primary bioenergy production without carbon capture and storage (variable “Primary Energy Biomass”)
E_{PBECCS}	Primary bioenergy production with carbon capture and storage (variable “Primary Energy Biomass w/ CCS”)
E_{SBE}	Secondary bioenergy production without carbon capture and storage (variable “Secondary Energy Electricity Biomass”)
E_{SBECCS}	Secondary bioenergy production with carbon capture and storage E_{SBECCS} (variable “Secondary Energy Electricity Biomass w/ CCS”).

We interpreted f_{BECCS}^* as the total fraction of bioenergy feedstock used for both LMTs making use of some form of CCS and distributed this fraction to BECCS and PyCCS depending on the scenario, country and year. As MESSAGE-GLOBIOM assumes BECCS, we express the deviation from the original data source via a sub-fraction being attributed to PyCCS according to:

$$f_{BECCS}^* = f_{BECCS} - f_{PyCCS} = x_{PyCCS} f_{BECCS}^* + (1 - x_{PyCCS}) f_{BECCS}^*. \quad (26)$$

Hence, the scenario inputs controlling the relative deployment of BECCS and PyCCS could be fully qualified by assumption on the relative share of PyCCS, i.e. x_{PyCCS} .

For the preliminary input dataset, we simply distributed the bioenergy feedstock treated with CCS to BECCS and PyCCS in equal shares ($x_{PyCCS}=0.5$). Thus, we added a control on the model simulations assuring the model provides a response in terms of carbon sequestration caused by both LMTs in the preliminary simulation results.

Initially, the LMT PyCCS was presented to stakeholders at the regional workshops of WP6 (see D6.2) as the production of biochar from purpose grown feedstock with application of the char to agricultural soils, in order to achieve a long-term storage of carbon and soil improvements. However, participants in all regional workshops pointed out that biochar should only be produced from agricultural or urban residues. Due to limitations of the modelling approach, it was not possible to

change the LMT in the model representation accordingly. Moreover, carbon storage in form of biochar based on purpose grown feedstock is in fact frequently discussed in literature as possible alternative to BECCS (e.g. Azzi et al., 2019; Smith, 2016; Werner et al., 2022; Woolf et al., 2010). Compared to BECCS, the technical readiness level of those pyrolysis-based technologies is higher and the technology can be implemented in rather small-scale facilities having less environmental impact than large-scale BECCS-plants. In addition, storage capacity for the biochar, i.e. agricultural cropland, is usually abundant, in contrast to special geological structure needed for BECCS. Because of these advantages, we consider PyCCS an alternative option to BECCS, particularly in low-income regions in the scenario with relatively lower regional engagement, which impedes the implantation of large-scale solutions. As biochar in soils potentially leads to improved soil properties (not covered by the model system), PyCCS can provide co-benefits for the abatement of other environmental issues (e.g. improved water quality due to lower fertilization requirements) and is therefore preferred over BECCS in the more balanced scenario “*Moderate CDR Ambition*”.

With the revised quantification of inputs for the LMTs PyCCS and BECCS we differentiated the four groups of countries:

- High-income countries and large single economies (OECD+CN+IN): This group is more able than other countries to implement cost-intensive, large-scale high-tech LMTs like BECCS (low x_{PyCCS}).
- Remaining countries in ASIA and REF: The relevance of BECCS was considered low by stakeholders (and Task 6.4 staff in the case of REF) but PyCCS was considered feasible (high x_{PyCCS}).
- Count in the LAM region: The relevance of BECCS was considered very low by stakeholders but PyCCS was considered feasible (high x_{PyCCS}).
- Countries in the MAF region: We assumed intermediate relevance of BECCS as it was not clearly flagged as unrealistic by stakeholders in the African workshop although such information was explicitly requested and those countries have limited financial resources.

These regional considerations, in which we attempted to address stakeholder feedback as much as possible, were combined with the general assumption that “*High CDR Ambition*” focused on large-scale high-tech LMTs like BECCS (corresponding to low x_{PyCCS}) where feasible, whereas “*Moderate CDR Ambition*” makes use of more balanced LMT portfolio preferring PyCCS. The resulting assumption are summarized in Table 9.

Table 9 Summary of assumptions on PyCCS LMT and BECCS LMT for the “Reference”, the “Corrected Reference” (SSP2-RCP4.5), and the LMT scaling scenarios, highlighting the changes between preliminary assumptions and final assumption after revision. Note: No revision of input data for “Reference”; no preliminary runs for “Corrected reference” (SSP2-RCP4.5).

Scenario	Region	Preliminary settings of χ_{PyCCS}	Final settings of χ_{PyCCS}
Reference	global	0	-
Corrected reference (SSP2-RCP4.5)	OECD + CN + IN	-	0.5, const.
	MAF		1, const.
	ASIA (remaining) + REF		1, const.
	LAM		1, const.
Moderate CDR Ambition	OECD + CN + IN	0.5, const.	0.5 (2015), 0.25 (2100)
	MAF		1 (2015), 0.7 (2100)
	ASIA (remaining) + REF		1, const.
	LAM		1, const.
High CDR Ambition	OECD + CN + IN	0.5, const.	0.5 (2015), 0 (2100)
	MAF		1 (2015), 0.5 (2100)
	ASIA (remaining) + REF		1 (2015), 0.75 (2100)
	LAM		1 (2015), 0.8 (2100)

4.4 Summary of assumptions by scenario

In the previous sections of this chapter, the assumptions and methods underlying the scenario quantification were presented with a focus on the different topics covered by the input dataset, i.e. information needed for a specific LMT or component of the coupled model system. In the following section, the characteristics of the two LMT scaling scenarios are briefly summarized in form of short storylines, explaining the main characteristics of the respective LMT portfolio.

4.4.1 The scenario “High CDR Ambition”

The scenario “High CDR Ambition” is mainly characterized by the coincidence of high ambitions to remove carbon dioxide from the atmosphere and strong regional engagement. There is a strong focus on the implementation of large-scale deployment LMTs, i.e. BECCS, aiming on the maximization of CDR. This development is accompanied by great efforts to reduce the area demand for food production, mainly due to crop yield improvements and dietary changes towards lower consumption of livestock products. Thus, the substantial increase in the production of bioenergy feedstock, in particular 2nd generation bioenergy crops, becomes possible through a reduction of the global cropland for food production and pastureland by about one third until the end of the century. Potential adverse effects of BECCS on environmental challenges other than climate change receive little attention. LMTs with relatively low CDR potential, e.g. agroforestry, are deployed at a rather low level, despite of their co-benefits for other goals of sustainable development. The main characteristics of the LMT portfolio area as follows:

- High-income countries and large economies are willing and capable to implement a substantial amount of cost-intensive large-scale BECCS facilities.
- The high level of regional engagement also leads to collaboration of smaller countries and countries with less financial resources enabling them to increase moderately the amount of bioenergy feedstock used for BECCS.
- Regionally, large areas no longer needed for livestock production are only partly compensated by additional bioenergy production, making room for afforestation. By the end of the century, the afforested area is almost as large as the newly established cropland for bioenergy.
- LMTs that can be implemented on existing agricultural land without a reduction of cropland productivity, e.g. conversion to no-tillage practices, are implemented at very high rates in high-income countries. In regions with lower financial capacity and less expertise, the conversion is somewhat slower, though it is consequently promoted by international schemes to cope with needed investments and campaigns of knowledge transfer.
- As practices of silvopasture do not change the area demand of the livestock sector they are widely adopted for their potential of CDR.
- Agroforestry, i.e. combination of (cash) crops and trees, is deployed only to a limited extent as needed to adapt to climate change. However, agroforestry is not considered a CDR measure as it would lead to larger area demand for food production because of the lower crop yields compared to sole crop production systems.

4.4.2 *The scenario "Moderate CDR Ambition"*

The scenario *"Moderate CDR Ambition"* is characterized by moderate ambitions to remove carbon dioxide from the atmosphere through measures taken in the land-use sector. Partly, this is because of moderate capacities due to a lack of regional engagement, which generally impedes the implementation of large-scale, international measures with high CDR potential (e.g. BECCS). However, there is also awareness that a one-dimensional focus on climate mitigation through CDR may lead to changes in land-use, e.g. large mono-culture plantations of bioenergy feedstock, that impair the possibilities to abate other environmental challenges such as biodiversity loss. Thus, the LMT portfolio deployed tries to balance multiple goals of sustainable development considering prevailing moderate mitigation capacities:

- Measures combining bioenergy production with carbon capture and storage are put in place with an emphasis on pyrolysis of biomass and carbon storage in form of biochar in agricultural soils (PyCCS), although such LMTs have a lower CDR potential. PyCCS combines the advantage of pyrolysis that it can be implemented economically on rather small scales with the beneficial effects of biochar on soil properties. Further, the storage technology bears lower environmental risks compared to storage of carbon dioxide in geological structures.
- PyCCS dominates in Latin America, Asia and, less pronounced, in Africa, while high-income industrial countries deploy slightly more BECCS.

- Moderate efforts to reduce the area demand for food production limit the deployment of PyCCS and BECCS.
- Land savings in the livestock sector do not allow afforesting a significant area, globally.
- Moderate mitigation capacities also limit the conversion of conventional agriculture to no-tillage practices.
- Agroforestry practices are widely adopted due to their co-benefits for biodiversity, income generation, and soil conservation. Agroforestry covers at least two thirds of the global cropland of annual crops by the end of the century.

5 Results of the scenario quantification

This chapter presents the results of the derivation of input data on the agricultural context from MESSAGE-GLOBIOM results as outlined in section 4.1 and the input data controlling the deployment of LMTs resulting from the assumptions described in section 3.3. To explain the rationale behind the assumptions for each LMT and their revision transparently, it was useful to present the preliminary assumptions. However, in the results we focus on the presentation of the final of model inputs in body of this deliverable. The preliminary model inputs and model results can be found in the annex⁴ of deliverable D6.2 (“Regional Engagement for Global Impact”) of deliverable 6.2.

5.1 Contextual input data on the development of the agricultural sector

Figure 2 compares globally aggregated dynamics of key variables describing the development of the agricultural and land-use sector used as the context of LMT deployment in the reference and LMT scaling scenarios. In Figure 2a) total cropland area and the split into areas for the production of food, fibers and bio-base materials and production of bioenergy feedstock (1st and 2nd generation) is shown. There are only minor differences in the extent of total cropland between the different variants, which grows by about 20% until 2100. In contrast, cropland area for food, feed, and bio-based materials (FFM, Figure 2a) decreases in the LMT scaling scenarios and is, by the end of the century, almost 50% lower in “*High CDR Ambition*” and 33% lower in “*Moderate CDR Ambition*” as compared to the reference. The reasons for the area decrease are yield improvements of about 60% (used in all reference and LMT scaling scenarios, Figure 2d) and reductions in crop production (Figure 2e), mainly animal feed, caused by dietary changes of the world population towards less meat consumption (Popp et al., 2017). The latter is more pronounced in “*High CDR Ambition*”. The “*Corrected Reference*” also shows a significantly reduced production and, hence, area for the production of crops for food, feed, and materials as compared to the uncorrected reference (“*Reference*”).

⁴ Annex D2: Modelling Assumptions and Results by region for Coupled Model (Landshift and LPJ-Guess)

Figure 2 Summary of the input data on the development of the agricultural sector used as context for LMT deployment.

A similar observation can be made for pasture area (Figure 2b) although the trend shows a decline (~10%) also in the “Reference” and “Corrected Reference” (the correction had no effect on pasture area). Again, the area reduction is stronger for “High CDR Ambition” (-35%) than for “Moderate CDR Ambition” (-24%). This translates into about 750 million hectares of afforested land in “High CDR Ambition” in 2100 and zero area left for afforestation in “Moderate CDR Ambition” (Figure 2c). In addition, the MESSAGE-GLOBIOM dataset provided information on the share of bioenergy feedstock feeding into technologies with CCS as shown in Figure 2f. While the amplitude of the change is approximately the same for all variants, the shift to a higher fraction of CCS starts about 20 years earlier in the LMT scaling scenarios (almost no differences between High and Moderate ambition) compared both reference scenarios.

Regionally, a number of deviations from the global trends can be observed (Figure 3). In Asia, total cropland extent grows only during the first one to two decades and begins to decline between 2040 (“High CDR Ambition”) and 2050 (“Moderate CDR Ambition”). In “Moderate CDR Ambition”, total cropland extent in 2100 is approximately that same as in the base year 2015, while it is almost 10% lower than in the base year in “High CDR Ambition”. These dynamics are due to particularly strong reduction of cropland demand for food, feed, and materials in this region. In contrast, there is only a small reduction of cropland for FFM compared to the “Reference” in Latin America (LAM, Figure 3b).

Figure 3 Development of cropland area derived from MESSAGE-GLOBIOM and LUH2 by scenario in five world regions

Nevertheless, the area for bioenergy crops grows significantly in this region as total cropland expands more than in other regions. In the MAF and REF regions, expansion of bioenergy cropland is limited and levels off in the second half of the century, reaching only about 1/3 of total cropland in 2100 (Figure 3 c and e). In the remaining regions, the extent of cropland for bioenergy exceeds that for food, feed and materials in “High CDR Ambition”, in LAM also for “Moderate CDR Ambition”. OECD countries have somewhat larger cropland extent than the “Reference” at the end of the century (Figure 3d) and show a reduction in cropland for FFM of more than 50% compared to the “Reference” in 2100.

The results aggregated to the four regional subset of countries used in the stakeholder workshops are shown in ANNEX C.

5.2 Input data for LMT deployment

The model input data to control LMT deployment, which result from the assumption described in section 4.3, are presented in terms of area allocated to the various LMTs in the “Reference” and LMT scaling scenario. The area was aggregated to the varying subsets of countries that were differentiated in the assumptions for individual LMTs.

Figure 4 shows how the assumption on the no-till LMT and the development of cropland area of annual crops translate into the cropland area managed with reduced or without tillage.

Figure 4 Cropland area of annual crops managed with no-tillage practices by scenario aggregated for the two regions with differing assumptions a) OECD countries, countries in Latin America, China, and India and b) remaining countries.

This area is zero in the “Reference” and “Corrected Reference” scenario. In the OECD countries, Latin America, China, and India, both LMT scaling scenarios lead to similar dynamics, though the absolute area is larger in “High CDR Ambition”. The trend peaks in 2050 and then decreases as the share of no-till no longer grows but the cropland area of annual crops starts declining. In the rest of the world, the no-till area grows until 2100 in “Moderate CDR Ambition”, while the decline of cropland used for annual crops and the increase of no-till portion of it compensate each other, leading to a more or less constant area from 2065 onwards.

The development of agroforestry and silvopasture is shown in Figure 5. The resulting reductions in crop yields are shown in Figure 6. In the “Reference” and “Corrected Reference” scenario, the LMT is not deployed. In both LMT scaling scenarios to area of agroforestry and silvopasture increases steadily over the whole century. In “Moderate CDR Ambition”, the area of agroforestry systems is highest and reaches about 480 million hectares. At the same time, silvopasture expands to about 284 million hectares. Whereas this has no adverse impacts on grassland productivity, it results in crop yields declining by about one quarter until 2100. In “High CDR Ambition”, the global area of silvopasture is higher (491 million hectares in 2100) while agroforestry only covers 180 million hectares at the end of the century. Consequently, the yield reduction is only about 15% by 2100.

Figure 5 Area of agroforestry and silvopasture by scenario aggregated for the two regions with differing assumptions a) OECD and reforming countries, China, and India and b) remaining countries.

Figure 6 Reduction in crop yields due to agroforestry and reduction in grassland productivity due to silvopasture by scenario aggregated for the two regions with differing assumptions a) OECD and reforming countries, China, and India and b) remaining countries.

The time series of the feedstock production area for BECCS (Figure 7 and Figure 8) is distinguished between 1st and 2nd generation bioenergy crops. Within a scenario, the four variables add up to the product of total cropland area for bioenergy and its share used for CCS-technologies (Figure 2a and f).

In the reference scenario, only the area for 1st generation bioenergy crops feeding into BECCS is greater than zero, as zero production of 2nd generation bioenergy crops was assumed and PyCCS is not deployed. In most regions, the variable shows the sigmoid of the CCS fraction in (Figure 2f) except for MAF where the growing production of food, feed, and materials in combination with maximum yield increase of 150% does not allow growing bioenergy crops after 2075 in the reference scenario. The revised assumptions of the “*Corrected Reference*” scenario actually result in bioenergy production in Africa until 2100. In this variant, the feedstock feeds partly into BECCS only for the OECD countries, China and India (Figure 7a), while in all other regions it is used entirely for PyCCS (Figure 8). As in the reference, there is no cultivation of 2nd generation bioenergy crops.

In “*Moderate CDR Ambition*”, bioenergy production feeds partly into BECCS only in OECD countries, China, India (Figure 7a) and the MAF region (Figure 7b), where the share of BECCS increases moderately over time. In all other regions, we assumed 100% PyCCS for the whole century. The relative contribution of 2nd generation bioenergy crops to the total grows until 2100 in OECD countries, China, India and the MAF region, while the fraction of 1st generation bioenergy crops in the feedstock mix grows in Asia, reforming countries, and Latin America towards the end of the century.

In “*High CDR Ambition*”, a gradual shift to BECCS is assumed, which is most pronounced in OECD countries, China and India where it ultimately reaches 100% (zero PyCCs in 2100, Figure 8a). The dynamics of the contribution of 1st and 2nd generation bioenergy crops is similar to that in “*Moderate CDR Ambition*”.

Figure 7 Area of feedstock production for BECCS by scenario aggregated for the four regions with differing assumptions: a) OECD countries plus China and India, b) countries in Africa and Middle East, c) countries in Asia (except CN and IN) and the reforming countries, and c) countries in Latin America

Figure 8 Area of feedstock production for PyCCS by scenario aggregated for the four regions with differing assumptions: a) OECD countries plus China and India, b) countries in Africa and Middle East, c) countries in Asia (except CN and IN) and the reforming countries, and c) countries in Latin America

6 Reflections on stakeholder engagement and modelling

In this section, we reflect on the limitations and uncertainties introduced, on the one hand, by the selection of the reference scenario and LMTs covered and, on the other hand, by the knowledge base and methods used to quantify model inputs. Limitations and uncertainties related to the model in general and the representation of LMTs in the model are discussed (or will be discussed) in the LANDMARC Deliverables of work package 7 (D7.1-D7.4).

The SSP2 scenario in combination with climate policies consistent with the RCP4.5 was set as the reference scenario already in the proposal of the LANDMARC project. In that way, we could build on an already existing complete model input dataset and could focus on the adaptation and extension of this dataset regarding certain aspects in order to compile the input dataset for the global LMT scaling scenarios. Anchoring the LMT scaling scenarios to SSP2 narrows the possibilities of land-use based climate mitigation as compared to, for example, the sustainability oriented pathway SSP1, which facilitates deeper emission cuts and a wider range of land mitigation options due to the socio-economic and demographic assumptions.

A major limitation of the quantitative LMT scaling scenarios presented here is the mismatch between LMTs covered and LMTs considered most relevant by stakeholders. As the group of stakeholders was carefully selected to be representative of the actors involved in planning of future LMT portfolios such a mismatch questions the relevance of our scenarios. Participants in our stakeholder engagement process could not easily provide or make use of quantitative information on LMTs, which are not relevant in their view. However, the main purpose of Task 6.4 was to provide input data for the global modelling experiments with the coupled model system in work package 7. Unfortunately, the possibilities of an accurate representation of different LMTs in the model system turned out to be very limited, leading to the small set of five LMTs addressed in this report. Modelling additional LMTs or substantial changes to the way LMTs are represented would have required elaborate model development, which was beyond the project resources and timeframe. For example, stakeholders frequently stated that the production and application of biochar from agricultural or urban residues is more relevant than biochar from purpose-grown feedstock. Other prominent examples of missing LMTs in our set are improved forest management, mainly stressed by stakeholders in Latin America, and BECCS based on woody biomass rather than crops, which was frequently asked for in the European workshop. We expect that some of these important aspects be tackled in future research (e.g. within the Horizon Europe project RESCUE).

The derivation of contextual input data on the development of the agricultural sector, i.e. the basic input requirements of LandSHIFT-G from output of an integrated assessment model is based on a number of simplifications and assumptions (see 4.1) needed to conduct the downscaling of regional data from MESSAGE-GLOBIOM to country level, which introduced uncertainty. For example, we assumed a globally uniform ratio of average yields of food crops and bioenergy crops. In reality, the ratio depends on the actual crop mix and therefore varies regionally. The effect of this simplification on the results was not studied in detail as information found in the supplementary information of

Fricko et al. (2017) confirmed that the assumed ratio is consistent with the underlying assumptions made in the IAM. In addition, another important simplification is assuming that the relative changes in cropland, pasture land, productivity, etc. found for one of the five large world regions are also valid for each country that belongs to that region. In reality, the agricultural sector of countries within the regions develop differently. Thus, our calculation can be unrealistic for individual countries, potentially causing, e.g., infeasible expansion of cropland exceeding the available and suitable land area.

The resulting input datasets for the LMT scaling scenarios represent substantial improvements of crop yields. Although food security for the same world population is assured, this allows freeing cropland area needed to produce food, feed, and materials in the reference scenario, a prerequisite for the deployment of LMTs requiring additional area. Participants of the stakeholder workshops frequently criticized the yield improvement as too optimistic. However, we were unable to adjust the yield improvement without losing consistency of the whole dataset. The IAM results used here constitute an internally consistent solution taking into account the complex interrelationships between the agricultural and energy sectors as well as the dynamics of demand and production of agricultural commodities via global trade. Hence, changing such a fundamental variable like crop yield would require dedicated IAM simulations. Our modelling system is also limited compared to a full IAM such as MESSAGE-GLOBIOM, which imposed a number of limitations on the scope of our work.

Initially, it was expected that the quantification of input variables controlling the deployment of LMTs would be informed largely by stakeholder feedback. This, however, turned out to be unrealistic, mainly because of the mismatch of LMTs covered by the model and considered relevant by stakeholders mentioned above. Hence, the quantification had to be done by researchers responsible for Task 6.4. Here, we had to be pragmatic, as the available processing time did not allow for an in-depth analysis of plausible potentials for the deployment of each LMT.

7 Conclusion

In conclusion, this deliverable describes two global scenarios of LMT implementation. This report focuses on the translation of qualitative scenario assumptions partly derived from regional stakeholder engagement into numerical values. The resulting datasets are tailored to serve as input for the global simulation studies with the coupled land-climate model developed in LANDMARC. Stakeholder contributions to the quantitative scenarios were limited to rather general comments regarding individual LMTs, mainly due to an insufficient overlap of LMTs covered by the model and LMTs considered most relevant by stakeholders. Nevertheless, stakeholder feedback was largely integrated with assumptions made by researchers responsible for Task 6.4 resulting in comprehensive input datasets as needed for the global climate modelling. Although the assumptions on the deployment of available LMTs are relatively simple, major regional differences in magnitude and temporal dynamics are covered.

The derivation of contextual input data on the development of the agricultural sector from results of an integrated assessment model relies on a number of simplifications and assumptions. Although internal consistency is ensured on the continental scale, the results may be unrealistic for individual countries.

Based on the input dataset presented in this report, simulation experiments have been performed. The results and potential policy implication will be presented in the Deliverables D7.2 (“Climate projections and LMT effects on global carbon cycle”), D7.3 (“Decadal climate predictions and LMT effects on global carbon cycle”), and D7.4 (“Economic and environmental effects of LMT implementation”).

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Annex A Countries covered by the coupled model system

Table A 1 Listing of countries covered by the global coupled model system and their mapping to regional definitions use for the preparation of inputs and stakeholder workshops: (i) data from MESSAGE-GLOBIOM was available as 5-region level aggregates, (ii) Tier1-region identifying the country subsets for the stakeholder workshops, (iii) “dominant climate conditions” used to select the representative parameters for modelling agroforestry.

Country name	Country ID in LandSHIFT-G	Code of 5-region level aggregate (MESSAGE) ⁵	Tier1-region for regional SH workshops	Dominant climate conditions
Afghanistan	4	R5.2ASIA		dry
Albania	8	R5.2OECD		dry
Algeria	12	R5.2MAF		dry
Angola	24	R5.2MAF		dry
Azerbaijan	31	R5.2REF		dry
Argentina	32	R5.2LAM		dry
Australia	36	R5.2OECD		dry
Austria	40	R5.2OECD	EU-27	wet
Bahrain	48	R5.2MAF		dry
Bangladesh	50	R5.2ASIA		tropical
Armenia	51	R5.2REF		dry
Belgium	56	R5.2OECD	EU-27	wet
Bhutan	64	R5.2ASIA		tropical
Bolivia	68	R5.2LAM	ACTO	mixed
Bosnia and Herzegovina	70	R5.2OECD		dry
Botswana	72	R5.2MAF		dry
Brazil	76	R5.2LAM	ACTO	mixed
Belize	84	R5.2LAM		tropical
Solomon Islands	90	R5.2ASIA		tropical
Brunei Darussalam	96	R5.2ASIA	ASEAN	tropical
Bulgaria	100	R5.2OECD	EU-27	dry
Myanmar	104	R5.2ASIA	ASEAN	tropical
Burundi	108	R5.2MAF	EAC	dry
Belarus	112	R5.2REF		dry
Cambodia	116	R5.2ASIA	ASEAN	tropical
Cameroon	120	R5.2MAF		mixed
Canada	124	R5.2OECD		wet
Central African Republic	140	R5.2MAF		mixed
Sri Lanka	144	R5.2ASIA		tropical
Chad	148	R5.2MAF		dry
Chile	152	R5.2LAM		mixed

⁵ <https://tntcat.iiasa.ac.at/SspDb/dsd?Action=htmlpage&page=10#regiondefs>

Country name	Country ID in LandSHIFT-G	Code of 5-region level aggregate (MESSAGE) ⁵	Tier1-region for regional SH workshops	Dominant climate conditions
China	156	R5.2ASIA		mixed
Colombia	170	R5.2LAM	ACTO	tropical
Congo	178	R5.2MAF		tropical
Congo, The Democratic Republic of the	180	R5.2MAF	EAC	tropical
Costa Rica	188	R5.2LAM		tropical
Croatia	191	R5.2OECD	EU-27	dry
Cuba	192	R5.2LAM		tropical
Cyprus	196	R5.2OECD	EU-27	dry
Czech Republic	203	R5.2OECD	EU-27	wet
Benin	204	R5.2MAF		mixed
Denmark	208	R5.2OECD	EU-27	wet
Dominican Republic	214	R5.2LAM		tropical
Ecuador	218	R5.2LAM	ACTO	tropical
El Salvador	222	R5.2LAM		tropical
Equatorial Guinea	226	R5.2MAF		tropical
Ethiopia	231	R5.2MAF		dry
Eritrea	232	R5.2MAF		dry
Estonia	233	R5.2OECD	EU-27	wet
Fiji	242	R5.2ASIA		tropical
Finland	246	R5.2OECD	EU-27	wet
France	250	R5.2OECD	EU-27	wet
French Guiana	254	R5.2LAM	ACTO	tropical
Djibouti	262	R5.2MAF		dry
Gabon	266	R5.2MAF		tropical
Georgia	268	R5.2REF		dry
Gambia	270	R5.2MAF		dry
Palestinian Territory, Occupied	275	R5.2MAF		dry
Germany	276	R5.2OECD	EU-27	wet
Ghana	288	R5.2MAF		mixed
Greece	300	R5.2OECD	EU-27	dry
Guatemala	320	R5.2LAM		tropical
Guinea	324	R5.2MAF		tropical
Guyana	328	R5.2LAM	ACTO	tropical
Haiti	332	R5.2LAM		tropical
Honduras	340	R5.2LAM		tropical
Hungary	348	R5.2OECD	EU-27	dry
Iceland	352	R5.2OECD		wet
India	356	R5.2ASIA		mixed
Indonesia	360	R5.2ASIA	ASEAN	tropical
Iran, Islamic Republic of	364	R5.2MAF		dry
Iraq	368	R5.2MAF		dry
Ireland	372	R5.2OECD	EU-27	wet
Israel	376	R5.2MAF		dry

Country name	Country ID in LandSHIFT-G	Code of 5-region level aggregate (MESSAGE) ⁵	Tier1-region for regional SH workshops	Dominant climate conditions
Italy	380	R5.2OECD	EU-27	dry
Cote d'Ivoire	384	R5.2MAF		mixed
Jamaica	388	R5.2LAM		tropical
Japan	392	R5.2OECD		wet
Kazakhstan	398	R5.2REF		dry
Jordan	400	R5.2MAF		dry
Kenya	404	R5.2MAF	EAC	dry
Korea, Democratic People's Republic of	408	R5.2ASIA		wet
Korea, Republic of	410	R5.2ASIA		wet
Kuwait	414	R5.2MAF		dry
Kyrgyzstan	417	R5.2REF		dry
Lao People's Democratic Republic	418	R5.2ASIA	ASEAN	tropical
Lebanon	422	R5.2MAF		dry
Lesotho	426	R5.2MAF		dry
Latvia	428	R5.2OECD	EU-27	wet
Liberia	430	R5.2MAF		mixed
Libyan Arab Jamahiriya	434	R5.2MAF		dry
Liechtenstein	438	R5.2OECD		wet
Lithuania	440	R5.2OECD	EU-27	wet
Luxembourg	442	R5.2OECD	EU-27	wet
Madagascar	450	R5.2MAF		mixed
Malawi	454	R5.2MAF		dry
Malaysia	458	R5.2ASIA	ASEAN	tropical
Mali	466	R5.2MAF		dry
Mauritania	478	R5.2MAF		dry
Mexico	484	R5.2LAM		mixed
Mongolia	496	R5.2ASIA		dry
Moldova, Republic of	498	R5.2REF		wet
Morocco	504	R5.2MAF		dry
Mozambique	508	R5.2MAF		mixed
Oman	512	R5.2MAF		dry
Namibia	516	R5.2MAF		dry
Nepal	524	R5.2ASIA		mixed
Netherlands	528	R5.2OECD	EU-27	wet
New Caledonia	540	R5.2ASIA		tropical
New Zealand	554	R5.2OECD		wet
Nicaragua	558	R5.2LAM		tropical
Niger	562	R5.2MAF		dry
Nigeria	566	R5.2MAF		mixed
Norway	578	R5.2OECD		wet
Pakistan	586	R5.2ASIA		dry
Panama	591	R5.2LAM		tropical
Papua New Guinea	598	R5.2ASIA		tropical
Paraguay	600	R5.2LAM		mixed

Country name	Country ID in LandSHIFT-G	Code of 5-region level aggregate (MESSAGE) ⁵	Tier1-region for regional SH workshops	Dominant climate conditions
Peru	604	R5.2LAM	ACTO	mixed
Philippines	608	R5.2ASIA	ASEAN	tropical
Poland	616	R5.2OECD	EU-27	wet
Portugal	620	R5.2OECD	EU-27	mixed
Guinea-Bissau	624	R5.2MAF		mixed
Timor-Leste	626	R5.2ASIA		tropical
Qatar	634	R5.2MAF		dry
Romania	642	R5.2OECD	EU-27	mixed
Russian Federation	643	R5.2REF		wet
Rwanda	646	R5.2MAF	EAC	mixed
Saudi Arabia	682	R5.2MAF		dry
Senegal	686	R5.2MAF		dry
Sierra Leone	694	R5.2MAF		mixed
Slovakia	703	R5.2OECD	EU-27	wet
Viet Nam	704	R5.2ASIA	ASEAN	tropical
Slovenia	705	R5.2OECD	EU-27	wet
Somalia	706	R5.2MAF		dry
South Africa	710	R5.2MAF		dry
Zimbabwe	716	R5.2MAF		dry
Spain	724	R5.2OECD	EU-27	dry
Western Sahara	732	R5.2MAF		dry
Sudan (former)	736	R5.2MAF	EAC	dry
Suriname	740	R5.2LAM	ACTO	tropical
Swaziland	748	R5.2MAF		dry
Sweden	752	R5.2OECD	EU-27	wet
Switzerland	756	R5.2OECD		wet
Syrian Arab Republic	760	R5.2MAF		dry
Tajikistan	762	R5.2REF		dry
Thailand	764	R5.2ASIA	ASEAN	tropical
Togo	768	R5.2MAF		mixed
United Arab Emirates	784	R5.2MAF		dry
Tunisia	788	R5.2MAF		dry
Turkey	792	R5.2OECD		dry
Turkmenistan	795	R5.2REF		dry
Uganda	800	R5.2MAF	EAC	mixed
Ukraine	804	R5.2REF		mixed
Macedonia, The Former Yugoslav Republic of	807	R5.2OECD		dry
Egypt	818	R5.2MAF		dry
United Kingdom	826	R5.2OECD		wet
Tanzania	834	R5.2MAF	EAC	mixed
United States	840	R5.2OECD		mixed
Burkina Faso	854	R5.2MAF		dry
Uruguay	858	R5.2LAM		mixed
Uzbekistan	860	R5.2REF		dry
Venezuela	862	R5.2LAM	ACTO	tropical

Country name	Country ID in LandSHIFT-G	Code of 5-region level aggregate (MESSAGE)⁵	Tier1-region for regional SH workshops	Dominant climate conditions
Yemen	887	R5.2MAF		dry
Serbia and Montenegro	891	R5.2OECD		mixed
Zambia	894	R5.2MAF		mixed

Annex B Initial share of no-till management by country

Table A 2 Listing of initial values of the area share in cropland of arable crops managed with reduced or no tillage. Blank cells indicate combination not found in the base map generated by LandSHIFT-G.

Country name	Country ID in LandSHIFT-G	CC3ann	CC3nfx	CC3per	CC4ann	CC4per
Afghanistan	4	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Albania	8	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
Algeria	12	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Angola	24	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Azerbaijan	31	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Argentina	32	0.37	0.46	0.00	0.45	0.00
Australia	36	0.19	0.30	0.00	0.01	0.00
Austria	40	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
Bahrain	48	0.00		0.00		
Bangladesh	50	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Armenia	51	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Belgium	56	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	
Bhutan	64	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
Bolivia	68	0.18	0.28	0.00	0.20	0.00
Bosnia and Herzegovina	70	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
Botswana	72	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Brazil	76	0.15	0.35	0.00	0.25	0.00
Belize	84	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Solomon Islands	90	0.00	0.00	0.00		
Brunei Darussalam	96	0.00		0.00		
Bulgaria	100	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
Myanmar	104	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Burundi	108	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Belarus	112	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
Cambodia	116	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Cameroon	120	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00
Canada	124	0.30	0.27	0.00	0.01	
Central African Republic	140	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Sri Lanka	144	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Chad	148	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Chile	152	0.04	0.07	0.00	0.06	0.00
China	156	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Colombia	170	0.02	0.02	0.00	0.04	0.00
Congo	178	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

Congo, The Democratic Republic of the	180	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Costa Rica	188	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Croatia	191	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
Cuba	192	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Cyprus	196	0.00	0.00	0.00		
Czech Republic	203	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
Benin	204	0.02	0.03	0.00	0.04	0.00
Denmark	208	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
Dominican Republic	214	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Ecuador	218	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
El Salvador	222	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Equatorial Guinea	226	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Ethiopia	231	0.05	0.04	0.00	0.06	0.00
Eritrea	232	0.19	0.14	0.00	0.09	0.00
Estonia	233	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
Fiji	242	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Finland	246	0.09	0.10	0.00	0.00	
France	250	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.01	
French Guiana	254	0.00	0.00	0.00		0.00
Djibouti	262	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
Gabon	266	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Georgia	268	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
Gambia	270	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
Palestinian Territory, Occupied	275	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
Germany	276	0.02	0.04	0.00	0.02	
Ghana	288	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.00
Greece	300	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	
Guatemala	320	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00
Guinea	324	0.01	0.02	0.00	0.02	0.00
Guyana	328	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Haiti	332	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Honduras	340	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Hungary	348	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	
Iceland	352	0.00				
India	356	0.10	0.11	0.00	0.10	0.00
Indonesia	360	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Iran, Islamic Republic of	364	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Iraq	368	0.03	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Ireland	372	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
Israel	376	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Italy	380	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	

Cote d'Ivoire	384	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Jamaica	388	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Japan	392	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Kazakhstan	398	0.03	0.01	0.00	0.01	
Jordan	400	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
Kenya	404	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Korea, Democratic People's Republic of	408	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
Korea, Republic of	410	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
Kuwait	414	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
Kyrgyzstan	417	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
Lao People's Democratic Repbulic	418	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Lebanon	422	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
Lesotho	426	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	
Latvia	428	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
Liberia	430	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Libyan Arab Jamahiriya	434	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Lithuania	440	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
Luxembourg	442	0.00			0.00	
Madagascar	450	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.04	0.00
Malawi	454	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00
Malaysia	458	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Mali	466	0.02	0.07	0.00	0.03	0.00
Mauritania	478	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Mexico	484	0.02	0.02	0.00	0.06	0.00
Mongolia	496	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
Moldova, Republic of	498	0.03	0.07	0.00	0.02	
Morocco	504	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Mozambique	508	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Oman	512	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
Namibia	516	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Nepal	524	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Netherlands	528	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
New Caledonia	540	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
New Zealand	554	0.23	0.01	0.00	0.10	
Nicaragua	558	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Niger	562	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Nigeria	566	0.04	0.08	0.00	0.04	0.00
Norway	578	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
Pakistan	586	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Panama	591	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Papua New Guinea	598	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

Paraguay	600	0.27	0.36	0.00	0.36	0.00
Peru	604	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Philippines	608	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Poland	616	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
Portugal	620	0.04	0.00	0.00	0.04	
Guinea-Bissau	624	0.11	0.08	0.00	0.22	0.00
Timor-Leste	626	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Qatar	634	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
Romania	642	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
Russian Federation	643	0.04	0.05	0.00	0.05	
Rwanda	646	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Saudi Arabia	682	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
Senegal	686	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Sierra Leone	694	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Slovakia	703	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
Viet Nam	704	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Slovenia	705	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
Somalia	706	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
South Africa	710	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.06	0.00
Zimbabwe	716	0.03	0.03	0.00	0.04	0.00
Spain	724	0.02	0.01	0.00	0.02	
Western Sahara	732	0.00			0.00	
Sudan (former)	736	0.02	0.02	0.00	0.03	0.00
Suriname	740	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Swaziland	748	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Sweden	752	0.00	0.00	0.00		
Switzerland	756	0.03	0.00	0.00	0.00	
Syrian Arab Republic	760	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
Tajikistan	762	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
Thailand	764	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Togo	768	0.02	0.02	0.00	0.00	
United Arab Emirates	784	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
Tunisia	788	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
Turkey	792	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Turkmenistan	795	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Uganda	800	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Ukraine	804	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.01	
Macedonia, The Former Yugoslav Republic of	807	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
Egypt	818	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
United Kingdom	826	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	
Tanzania	834	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00

United States	840	0.21	0.16	0.00	0.17	0.00
Burkina Faso	854	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.00
Uruguay	858	0.28	0.45	0.00	0.37	0.00
Uzbekistan	860	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
Venezuela	862	0.05	0.05	0.00	0.12	0.00
Yemen	887	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Serbia and Montenegro	891	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
Zambia	894	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.03	0.00

Annex C Basic model input on the land-use sector by region

In this annex the basic contextual model inputs for the land-use sector are shown as aggregated to the set of countries, which were in the focus of the four regional stakeholder workshops (see also Table A 1):

- Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN);
- Member states of the European Union (EU27);
- Member countries of the Amazon Cooperation Treaty Organisation (ACTO) and
- Countries of the East African Community (EAC).

Figure A 1 Summary of the input data on the development of the agricultural sector used as context for LMT deployment aggregated for ASEAN countries.

Figure A 2 Summary of the input data on the development of the agricultural sector used as context for LMT deployment aggregated for EU27 countries.

Figure A 3 Summary of the input data on the development of the agricultural sector used as context for LMT deployment aggregated for ACTO countries.

Figure A 4 Summary of the input data on the development of the agricultural sector used as context for LMT deployment aggregated for EAC countries.